

TRANS

lighthouses

MORE THAN GREEN

Lighthouses
of transformative
nature-based solutions
for inclusive communities

Deliverable D1.1

Communication, dissemination
and exploitation plan v1

Funded by
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Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan v1

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

EC: European Commission

EEAB: External Ethical Advisory Board

EU: European Union

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679)

KPI: Key Performance Indicator

KER: Key Exploitable Result

NBS: Nature Based Solutions

SMEs: Small and Medium-sized Enterprises

WP: Work Package

Executive summary

Deliverable D1.1 is the first version of the plan for communication, dissemination and exploitation of results of the TRANS-lighthouses project. This initial plan contains information on how the consortium organises:

- the effective **communication** of the project's objectives and findings;
- the **interactions** among consortium members;
- the knowledge **dissemination** to relevant audiences;
- the maximisation of impact and **exploitation** of the project's results.

The plan for communication, dissemination and exploitation of results is strategically underpinned by the core of the TRANS-lighthouses' objectives in terms of living knowledge co-construction, knowledge sharing and synergies building, being transversely operationalized across the work packages. Therefore, the plan is based on the following **8 objectives mirrored in the work plan**:

1. Raise awareness about the project's activities and results;
2. Showcase the plurality of models, strategies and findings from a diversity of contexts;
3. Co-disseminate living knowledge;
4. Bring science to citizens and policy makers;
5. Develop roadmaps, tools and capacity building for co-governance innovations towards co-creation of nature-based solutions (NBS);
6. Achieve visibility in the local communities and document the process of local actions;
7. Better communicate the science of NBS, by supporting citizens' local knowledges and enhancing mutual trust;
8. Potentialize research data and knowledge in terms of intellectual property.

This initial version of the plan not only defines strategies, activities and expected results according to different target audiences, corresponding messages and tools, but it also details the communication of the project in terms of image/identity, as well as tools and channels through which awareness is to be raised about the activities and outputs of the project. Consequently, it anticipates and integrates contents expected in the **deliverable D1.3** consisting of a **dissemination package**, namely by covering the communication templates and materials already available and those under development, as well as the project's institutional profile and messaging, i.e. a project overview, which constitutes the basis for the development of fact sheet, leaflet/flyer and posters to support partners in networking activities and public events. The plan also covers the project's digital strategy in terms of website and social media, as expected in **deliverable D1.4**, consisting of the **website, newsletter and social media accounts** which are under development.

As a result, the plan firstly gives an **overview of the TRANS-lighthouses project**, including its abstract, the composition of its consortium, the definition of its ambition and approach, its objectives and work plan, assessment cases and pilot cases, as well as a **stakeholders analysis**. This analysis identifies the following 7 categories of stakeholders, their communication preferences and interests: i) project teams and partners; ii) researchers, scientists, students and educators; iii) funding agencies and stakeholders in general; iv) policy makers, government officials, local authorities; v) media and journalists; vi) citizens, local communities, and general public; vii) civil society organisations, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), social enterprises, and practitioners.

Secondly, the plan enters in a more specific and detailed way the project's communication, dissemination and exploitation of results. After defining these three aspects, the **objectives and corresponding measures** are presented, followed by **main activities, target audiences, channels and tools**, and the **development of the project's narrative, messages and language**. In respect to the latter, it includes:

- The project's **brand** and its application;
- Communication **templates** and **materials** already developed and others under development;
- **Communication and interaction adapted to the local contexts throughout work packages**:
 - > *work package 6*: community-based communication and citizen science;
 - > *work package 5*: local communication and documentation of the process;

- > *work package 4*: dissemination and replication of co-governance, and amplifying youth involvement;
- > *work package 3*: democracy labs as interfaces between science and policies;
- > *work package 2*: co-dissemination of living knowledge;
- **Events and publication channels**, based on a tentative schedule and preliminary selection;
- The project's **digital strategy**, covering internal communication, public repository, website, social media;
- **Awareness raising and development of guidelines** regarding images and messaging, gender, sustainability and accessibility.

Next, the plan details **how the effectiveness of communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts will be assessed**. On the one hand, TRANS-lighthouses project manager has developed **tracking tools** to support the collection of data about dissemination and communication activities for reporting purposes. These are collaborative tools which will enable all partners to: be aware of their obligations in relation to communication and dissemination; inform and keep track of communication and dissemination activities and outcomes; support the consortium internal reporting, as well as to report to the funding authority. These tools cover: consortium channels; dissemination reporting; communication reporting; press and media.

On the other hand, in addition to defining key performance indicators (KPIs) and to providing an initial identification of key exploitable results (KERs), the project also incorporates **reflexive monitoring**, as set out in the framework of task 6.1, which applies across work packages. This learning environment provides insight into the progress of the project in real time, assessment of processes in terms of goals achievement, and learning outcomes.

Task 1.5, dedicated to communication and dissemination, and work package 6, which develops community-based communication and citizen science, have also joined efforts to **know the communication capabilities and tools/channels that each partner manages**, by means of a communications survey. As a follow up, a **group of "communications contact persons"** identified through the survey will be invited to constitute a communications interface. This interface is aimed at **supporting the collection of data** about dissemination and communication activities for reporting purposes (c.f. collaborative monitoring/tracking tool), **as well as the assessment** of the communication objectives and of the partners' environment and communicative capacity.

It will also contribute to the **refinement of KPIs**, as quantifiable indicators of progress toward specific objectives and/or intended results, **and KERs**, corresponding to the identification of main interesting results which are selected and prioritised due to their high potential to be "exploited". Accordingly, the preliminary identification of KERs will be updated during the project, e.g. some might merge or be defined in a different way, and/or new ones might be considered.

Additionally, the project is developing **measurement and assessment frameworks and referenced guidelines for monitoring and evaluation in relation to gender, sustainability and accessibility**, with a particular focus on the organisation of meetings and events, as well as for the development of the project's website. Frameworks and guidelines will be tested and fine-tuned with recommendations, indicators and assessments emerging from our work together, since the TRANS-lighthouses project is committed to assessing the extent to which it can introduce these guidelines.

Consequently, learning outcomes will feed into two **updates of the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan**, tools, materials and activities. Deliverables D1.7 and D1.9 will report on the implementation of the plan, respectively at months 30 and 40 of the project.

Moreover, the initial plan identifies **roles and responsibilities and corresponding resources among partners** for its execution, including:

- project coordinator;
- steering committee;
- work package 6 participants (communication and interaction approaches, pathways, channels and tools adapted to local contexts);
- group of communications contact persons (identified by each partner);
- local partners of pilot cases and of assessment cases;

- associated partners (non-EU);
- all partners (art. 17 of Grant Agreement, transversal operationalisation, monitoring, inform and share).

Finally, the plan addresses **risk assessment, ethics compliance, and data privacy** in reference to:

- general risks in international and interdisciplinary projects;
- communications critical risks screened for the grant preparation;
- the SWOT analysis on the dissemination capacity of partners resulting from the communications survey developed with work package 6;
- the External Ethical Advisory Board, ethical guidelines to be defined in task 2.5, and other ethical standards, as well as the attention to be paid to informed consent and in disclosing information on assessment and pilot cases;
- TRANS-lighthouses' data management plan;
- the project's website security certificates, and the need to clearly communicate its privacy policy and data handling practices.

1. Project overview

1.1. Abstract

The TRANS-lighthouses project aims to understand the strengths and limitations in the design and implementation of nature-based solutions. Based on material and immaterial evidence, it proposes to contribute to rethinking and reframing the main elements that compose the complexity of creating socially and ecologically just solutions.

As a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme (grant agreement 101084628), lasting from May 2023 to October 2026 and with a budget 5.9 million euros, TRANS-lighthouses strengthens socio-politics as part of the public agenda for nature-based solutions towards systemic change.

TRANS-lighthouses also integrates a network of "lighthouses" in urban, rural, coastal and forest areas. The "lighthouses" are a metaphor for a set of local governance arrangements and instruments, within multi-stakeholder networks and concerted groups.

They are aimed at improving the contributions of nature-based solutions and achieving, in an integrated way, ecological, social and economic objectives. To this end, new governance models will be tested, as well as approaches and tools for co-creation in small scale but big picture projects that can be upscaled over time.

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101084628>

Figure 1: CORDIS profile

Accordingly, each lighthouse is composed of living knowledge labs, assessment cases, pilot cases and international associated partners. In these spaces, the interaction of different knowledges, experiences and roles will support the assessment of ongoing solutions and the testing of new ones. In this way, it is intended to prioritise the perspectives of citizens, in dialogue with other interested actors for their co-creation.

Figure 2: TRANS-lighthouses map

1.2. Consortium

The consortium of TRANS-lighthouses project comprises research and innovation performing organisations, policy-making institutions and civil society organisations, with 19 European partners from 10 countries. In terms of international cooperation, TRANS-lighthouses also integrates 9 associated partners from 7 countries in the Americas, Africa and Asia.

Table 1: EU participants

International cooperation / Associated partners

Universidad de Chile	Chile
Universidad de Buenos Aires	Argentina
Universidade de Brasília	Brazil
Prefeitura de São Paulo	Brazil
Tata Institute of social sciences	India
University of Illinois	USA
University of Dar es Salaam	Tanzania
Polycom Development Project	Kenya
Rede de Incubadoras Universitárias de Apoio e Fomento à Economia Solidária do Paraná - RIU	Brazil

Table 2: Associated partners

1.3. Ambition and approach

The project's ambition is to become a European reference in terms of socio-political challenges, in order to locally support nature-based projects and solutions. The assessment of the benefits and effects of solutions already developed aims to recognize practices and disseminate more economically and socially fair guidelines for their implementation.

Therefore, the acronym of the project TRANS-lighthouses stands for:

MORE THAN GREEN - Lighthouses of transformative nature-based

T ransformative	contributing to the full potential of NBS with communities
R eflexive	grounded in assessment and critical analysis
A ctivist	aiming at socioeconomic and political changes
N etworked	acting together across borders, disciplines and sectors
S olutions	multidimensional and nature-based governance
lighthouses	leading research in action

Table 3: Acronym

Conceptual approach

Network – diversity & community of practice	Network of NBS' lighthouses for inclusive communities, in urban, rural, coastal and forested areas, bringing together a diversity of European and international partners.
Interlinking metaphor – enhancing NBS contributions	Metaphor for a set of local arrangements and instruments grounded on a concerted and networked group of multiple actors committed to enhancing NBS contributions towards interlinked ecological, social and economic targets.
Testing small scale, but big-picture projects	Approach for testing new governance models and co-creation approaches and tools on small scale but big-picture projects that can be upscaled over time.
Living knowledge labs, assessment cases, pilot cases & international observers	Dedicated to assessing ongoing NBS and testing new ones, prioritising the perspectives of citizens and stakeholders for valuing and co-creating NBS.

Table 4: Conceptual approach

1.4. Objectives and work plan

Objectives	
	<p>1. GATHERING transdisciplinary perspectives through North-South community of practice</p> <hr/> <p>2. EXPANDING NBS definition through a reflexive framework to recognize diverse forms of knowledge</p> <hr/> <p>3. UNDERSTANDING the range of potential and limitations in NBS design and implementation</p> <hr/> <p>4. POLITICISING governance for just transition</p> <hr/> <p>5. EMBEDDING co-creation processes into governance arrangements</p> <hr/> <p>6. GUIDING an engaged and transformative communication</p>

Table 5: Project's objectives

Work plan / Work packages

Work packages	Leading partner
1 Project and consortium management Overall coordination of the work plan and consortium / Gender+ dimension	CES-UC Portugal
2 Living knowledge co-production and Place-based research Expanding the conventional approaches to NBS by developing reflexive and critical frameworks	RUC Denmark
3 Research in action and assessment Research, assessment and deepening the analysis of social, political and cultural contexts.	TUM Germany
4 Innovative governance for NBS co-creation Gathering partners with experience in research and intervention regarding participatory models of governance	CES-UC Portugal
5 Pilot cases implementation through co-creation Interconnects the research activities with real-world co-creation cases	Cyl Cyprus
6 Community-based communication and citizen science Communication and interaction with citizens in the deployment of NBS	uni. Eiffel-CNRS France
7 Ethics requirements Sets out the 'ethics requirements' the project must comply with	CES-UC Portugal

Table 6: Work plan / Work packages

1.5. Assessment cases and pilot cases

Assessment cases			Pilot cases		
Location	Connecting lighthouses	Leading partner	Location	Connecting lighthouses	Leading partner
Brussels / Belgium	>	Brussels	Brussels / Belgium	>	Brussels
Bologna / Italy	>	Sapienza	Rome / Italy	>	Sapienza
Troodos / Cyprus	>>	Cyl	Strovolos / Cyprus	>>	Cyl
Estarreja / Portugal	>	CME	Estarreja / Portugal	>	CME
Barcelos / Portugal	>>	CMB	Barcelos / Portugal	>>	CMB
Lagoa / Portugal	>>	UAc	Azores / Portugal	>>>	UAc
Regenerative farming network / Denmark	>	RUC	Regenerative farming network / Denmark	>	RUC
Madrid / Spain	>>	UEx	Cáceres / Spain	>>	EBR
Upper Allgäu / Germany	>	TUM			
Moisdon-la-Rivière / France	>	NU-CNRS			

> Coastal > Urban > Rural > Forestry

Table 7: Assessment and pilot cases

1.6. Stakeholders analysis: categories, communication preferences and interests

Stakeholders categories	Communication preferences and interests
Project teams and partners	→ share information, updates, and resources
	→ potential partners and collaborators from other countries and projects
Researchers, scientists, students and educators	→ project's findings
	→ methodologies
	→ opportunities for collaboration
	→ educational components and resources
	→ workshops
	→ training opportunities
Funding agencies and stakeholders in general	→ project's updates
	→ progress reports
	→ financial information
	→ project's outcomes
Policy makers, government officials, local authorities	→ alignment with EU policies and priorities
	→ project's impact on policy development
Media and journalists	→ public awareness and media coverage of the project
	→ easy access to press releases, and media resources
	→ contact information for media inquiries
Citizens, local communities, and general public	→ educational resources
	→ outreach materials
	→ information on the societal benefits of the research
Civil society organisations, SMEs, social enterprises, and practitioners	→ project's innovations
	→ project's technologies
	→ potential for partnerships

Table 8: Stakeholders categories, communication preferences and interests

2. Communication, dissemination and exploitation of results

2.1. Preliminary definitions

	Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation
What	Inform, promote and communicate activities and results	Make knowledge and results publicly available free-of-charge	Make concrete use of results for commercial, societal and political purposes
For whom	Citizens, stakeholders and the media	Who can learn and benefit from the results, such as: scientists, industry, public authorities, policymakers, civil society	Who can take the results forward or invest in them, such as: researchers, stakeholders, industry (also SMEs), public authorities, policymakers, civil society
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Having a well-designed strategy > Conveying clear messages > Using the right channels 	Publishing results in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Scientific magazines; > Scientific and/or targeted conferences > Databases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Creating roadmaps, prototypes, software > Sharing knowledge, skills, data
When	From the start until the end of the action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Anytime, as soon as results become available > Up to four years after the end of the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Towards the end of the action and beyond, as soon as exploitable results are available > Up to four years after the end of the project
Ks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Project's key result: key tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights. > Key Performance Indicator (KPI): quantifiable indicator of progress toward a specific objective and/or intended result. > Key Exploitable Result (KER): identified main interesting result which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be "exploited" – meaning to make use and derive benefits - downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education. Criteria: a) degree of innovation; b) exploitability; c) impact. 		

Table 9: Communication, dissemination, exploitation, results and indicators
Adapted from (European Commission, 2023) and Horizon Results Platform

2.2. Objectives and measures across project's key results and work packages

The plan for communication, dissemination and exploitation of results is strategically underpinned by the core of the TRANS-lighthouses' objectives in terms of living knowledge co-construction, knowledge sharing and synergies building, being transversely operationalized across the work packages. Therefore, the plan is based on the following 8 objectives mirrored in the work plan.

Figure 3: Communication, dissemination and exploitation of results: Objectives

Transversal operationalisation across project's key results work packages		
Project's key results	Objectives and measures	Work packages & tasks
1. The project's successful implementation	<p>→ 1. Raise awareness about the project's activities and results</p> <p>> 1.1. Set out how the consortium organises the communication of the project in terms of image/identity, as well as tools and channels through which awareness is raised about activities and results</p> <p>> 1.2. Coordination, monitoring and appropriation of communication and dissemination tools and channels</p>	Tasks 1.1, 1.5, 1.6 (connection with work package 6)
2. Community of practice	<p>→ 2. Showcase the plurality of models, strategies and findings from a diversity of contexts</p> <p>> 2.1. Involving associated partners in a community of practice</p>	Tasks 1.2, 1.3
3. Expanded conceptual framework and assessment for NBS	<p>→ 3. Co-disseminate living knowledge</p> <p>> 3.1. Scientific dissemination of expanded conceptual framework and assessment for NBS</p> <p>> 3.2. Developing ways for inclusive knowledge and practice dissemination</p>	Work packages 2 & 3 (connection with work package 6)
4. Science for citizens and policy makers	<p>→ 4. Bring science to citizens and policy makers</p> <p>> 4.1. Living no one behind in research</p> <p>> 4.2. Providing a space for long-term relationships with policy makers</p>	Tasks 3.3, 3.6 (connection with task 6.5)
5. Co-governance innovations towards co-creation of NBS	<p>→ 5. Develop roadmaps, tools and capacity building for co-governance innovations towards co-creation of NBS</p> <p>> 5.1. Production of transition roadmaps for the replication of co-governance methodologies</p> <p>> 5.2. Amplifying youth and older adults' involvement with research and guidelines for the co-creation of NBS</p>	Tasks 4.4, 4.5 (connection with task 6.4)
6. Living Knowledge(s) Labs	<p>→ 6. Achieve visibility in the local communities and document the process of local actions</p> <p>> 6.1. Communication for social mobilisation and citizen engagement.</p> <p>> 6.2. Documentation of local action and practice</p>	Tasks 5.1, 5.2, 5.5 (connection with work package 6)
7. Citizen science global framework for NBS	<p>→ 7. Better communicate the science of NBS, by supporting citizens' local knowledges and enhancing mutual trust</p> <p>> 7.1. Developing a citizen science global framework for NBS</p>	Work package 6
8. Research data and knowledge	<p>→ 8. Potentialize research data and knowledge in terms of intellectual property</p> <p>> 8.1. Compliance with open access principles</p> <p>> 8.2. Management and protection</p> <p>> 8.3. Ethics compliance</p>	Work packages 1 & 7, task 2.5

Table 10: Transversal operationalisation

2.3. Key activities, target audiences, channels and tools

#. Project's key results #Work packages & Tasks	Activities	Target audiences	Channels & tools
1. The project's successful implementation → Awareness about activities and results <i>T 1.1, 1.5, 1.6</i> <i>(connection with WP6)</i>	Definition of communication policy, procedures and objectives by the steering committee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers - Practitioners - Policy makers - Public at large 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organisation of events (kick-off/closing, conference/school) - public communications/exhibitions/workshops - participation of partners in events
	Design of communication tools to support the development of communication materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consortium members - Associated partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - brand and application guidelines - communication templates - website, newsletter template, social media accounts - database (images, news, inputs and metrics)
	Development of communication materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers - Practitioners - Policy makers - Local stakeholders, communities and citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fact sheet/project overview, leaflet/flyer, posters, video - contributions to the project's website and social media posts - bi-annual newsletter - press releases
	Divulgence of the project in the websites and newsletters of international networks and stakeholders, traditional media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers - Practitioners - Policy makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - media appearances (TV/radio) - publications in specialised magazines/journals, blogs
	Development of interactions among consortium members, as well as tools and platforms for project management and team communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consortium members - Researchers - Practitioners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - monthly online meetings of the steering committee - in-person/online consortium meetings, technical visits - monitoring and planning reports by work package - project's workflow and standard quality procedures - Gender Equality and Diversity (GED) focal point - internal communication platform
2. Community of practice → Plurality of models, strategies and findings showcased from a diversity of contexts <i>T 1.2, 1.3</i>	Knowledge sharing and synergies building among partners, and in the framework of clustering activities with other projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consortium members - Researchers - Practitioners - EU funded projects - Associated partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - internal and/or open webinars - clustering with projects/liaison with networks - collaborations with sibling projects - compilation and analysis on sharing and synergies
	Involving associated partners in a community of practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consortium members - Associated partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - webinars - participation in technical visit and/or consortium event - compilation and analysis on sharing and synergies - publication based on North-South cross comparison
3. Expanded conceptual framework and assessment for NBS → Living knowledge to be co-disseminated <i>WPs 2 & 3</i> <i>(connection with WP 6)</i>	Scientific dissemination of expanded conceptual framework and assessment for NBS carried out by partners in international referenced publications and conferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers - Practitioners - Policy makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - papers in international referenced publications - presentations and publications in international and referenced conferences
	Inclusive knowledge and practice dissemination, by means of unconventional initiatives of knowledge sharing, such as local community events, local media, and networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local stakeholders, communities and citizens - Local networks - Social economy sector - Local and regional business initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - local community events of scientific knowledge dissemination - project presentations in local media - clustering and liaison with networks
4. Science for citizens and policy makers	Results are shared and made accessible throughout the research process by means of internal living documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consortium members - Local stakeholders, communities and citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - internal living documents - translation into local languages
	Democracy labs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy makers: local government officials, politicians 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organisation of democracy labs

<p>→ Living no one behind in research and long-term relationships</p> <p><i>T 3.3, 3.6 (connection with T 6.5)</i></p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Practitioners: civil society organisations, municipal staff - Researchers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - policy briefs, infographics, videos and serious gaming
<p>5. Co-governance innovations towards co-creation of NBS</p> <p>→ Replication and amplification</p> <p><i>T 4.4, 4.5 (connection with T 6.4)</i></p>	<p>Production of transition roadmaps for the replication of co-governance methodologies and the facilitation of enabling environments for co-creation of NBS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local stakeholders, communities and citizens, local organisations, SMEs, social enterprises - Policy makers: politicians - Practitioners: civil society organisations, municipal staff - Researchers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - roadmaps disseminated through workshops for co-governance, policy briefs, videos and serious gaming (see democracy labs activities and outputs)
<p>6. Living Knowledge(s) Labs</p> <p>→ Visibility and documentation</p> <p><i>T 5.1, 5.2, 5.5 (connection with WP 6)</i></p>	<p>The communication strategies for social mobilisation and citizen engagement are devised with the communities and participants, supported by frameworks, guidelines and tools developed in WP6</p>	<p>Local stakeholders, communities and citizens</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - establishment and documentation of labs - participatory budgeting processes - graphic and text material about the aims of pilots - adaptations of the communication materials for local use
<p>7. Citizen science global framework for NBS</p> <p>→ Community-based communication and assessment</p> <p><i>WP 6</i></p>	<p>Mobilisation of citizens' local knowledges and development of trust:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Reflexive monitoring approach to finetune living global framework, which showcases approaches and pathways > Youth involvement in community-based communication for NBS 	<p>Local stakeholders, communities and citizens</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - living global framework of citizen science for NBS - portfolio of participatory methods - digital platform co-created with youth, including subsites - social media accounts and media campaigns with youth
<p>8. Research data and knowledge</p> <p>→ Accessibility, preservation and ethics compliance</p> <p><i>WPs 1 & 7, T 2.5</i></p>	<p>Compliance with open access principles</p> <p>Management and protection:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Data management plan > Internal collaborative communication tools with restricted access <p>Elaboration and application of ethics requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Principles and procedures established under task 2.5 > Work package 7 covering ethics requirements > Dissemination among consortium members > Ethics documents kept on file and submitted upon request by coordinator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local stakeholders, communities and citizens - Researchers - Practitioners - Policy makers <p>Consortium members</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consortium members - Local stakeholders, communities and citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - integration of open access principles - resources available on the project's website - publications on open research platforms - publications with free access to readers (afforded fee) - regulations in consortium agreement - updated data management plan - ethics deliverables - ethics board & meetings - activation of focal points and local ethics channels - guidance on research ethics and inclusive participation - webinars for dissemination and appropriation - translation into local languages

Table 11: Key activities, target audiences, channels and tools

2.4. Development of narrative, messages and language

2.4.1. Brand

> From small-scale/big-picture projects to shining rays

From small-scale/big-picture projects to shining rays

Created by Flatart
from Noun Project

From presentation template - [Communications project's database on Basecamp / Templates](#)

From presentation template - [Communications project's database on Basecamp / Templates](#)

From Pictures & Videos database on Basecamp / [Kick-off event - June 2023](#)

Funded by
the European Union

From [Communications project's database on Basecamp / Brand-Logo](#)

From [Download centre for visual elements](#)

Table 12: Brand: from small-scale/big-picture projects to shining rays

> Application guidelines

Brand application guidelines	
Basic usage guidelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Never change or distort the logo. - Never use different typefaces or colours. - Ensure good logo legibility, namely by using adequate size and colour version.
Vertical application MAIN	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> </div> </div>
Monochromatic negative versions	<p>To be used when a colour version is not possible.</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> </div>
Colour / negative versions	<p>Anticipating different brand applications, two coloured versions are defined to be used over the following background colours: corporate orange and grey.</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> </div>
Minimum sizes and safety margins	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Usage of logo below the indicated sizes should be avoided. - Also, in order to guarantee good logo legibility, no other visual elements should be present within the specified safety margins <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> </div>
Colour codes	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>PANTONE 432 C CMYK 70 54 60 37 RGB 68 79 76 HEX #444f4c RAL 6018</p> </div> </div>
Logo usage on different colour backgrounds	<p>On coloured backgrounds, the choice of the logo version should always favour the best contrast possible.</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> </div>
Typography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raleway - Open Font License - https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Raleway
EU emblem and funding statement art. 17 - Grant agreement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of the EU emblem in communication, displayed prominently and correctly, in combination with a simple funding statement - Ready-to-use funding statements/download centre for visual elements (in all EU languages, and in 14 non-EU languages): https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en - In publications, reports and more complex written document/materials use also: <i>"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them".</i> <div style="text-align: right; margin-top: 20px;"> <p>Funded by the European Union</p> </div>

From [Communications project's database on Basecamp / Brand-Logo](#)

Table 13: Brand application guidelines

2.4.2. Communication templates and materials

All communication templates and materials are compiled and made accessible to partners on the Basecamp internal collaborative platform: [ITRANS-LI Headquarters > Docs & Files > Communications](#).

As established under task 1.5 on communication and dissemination, the communication templates and materials will be produced:

- in such a way that they can be appropriated and adapted by teams for local use and dissemination to target local stakeholders, communities and citizens;
- in English, considering that translation into local languages will be provided by the respective consortium partners (Portugal, Denmark, Germany, Cyprus, France, Belgium, Italy, Spain) and associated partners (Chile, Argentina, Brazil, India, USA, Tanzania, Kenya);
- in consultation with the participants of work package 6 dedicated to community-based communication and citizen science.

Communication templates and materials			Version / Update
Types of material	Purpose / Description / Use / Snapshots		
Institutional profile and messaging	<p>> Project overview included in communication, dissemination and exploitation plan</p> <p>> Basis for the development of fact sheet, leaflet/flyer and posters to support partners in networking activities and public events</p> <p>1. Project overview 1.1. Abstract 1.2. Consortium 1.3. Ambition and approach 1.4. Objectives and work plan 1.5. Assessment cases and pilot cases 1.6. Stakeholders analysis: categories, communication preferences and interests</p>	V1	
Template of project presentations	<p>> .ppt file with a summary of the project to be used and adapted by partners in their project presentations</p>	V1	

Materials for events

- > Roll-up
- > Badges
- > Invitation letter
- > Certificate of attendance

Print and digital materials to be reused in all events

> Roll-up

> Badges

> Invitation letter

> Certificate of attendance

Print and digital materials to be reused in all events

V1

Organisation of consortium meetings

- > Booklet of kick-off event
- > Memory of kick-off event
- > Agenda of online consortium meetings
- > Work packages presentations: Reporting & Planning

Agenda/programme, dynamics, workshops, visits, practical information: formats, methodologies, materials as inspiration and lessons learned for all consortium meetings

> Booklet of kick-off event

> Memory of kick-off event

> Agenda of online consortium meetings

> Work packages presentations: Reporting & Planning

Agenda/programme, dynamics, workshops, visits, practical information: formats, methodologies, materials as inspiration and lessons learned for all consortium meetings

V1

Padlet

- > Launched at the kick-off event held in June 2023, in Azores as "Photographic Mosaic"
- > The concept is an inspiring experiment for participants to record their emotions, visions and perspectives
- > The participants were challenged to take pictures of elements that relate to the acronym of "TRANS-lighthouses"

To be continued and embedded on the website

> Launched at the kick-off event held in June 2023, in Azores as "Photographic Mosaic"

> The concept is an inspiring experiment for participants to record their emotions, visions and perspectives

> The participants were challenged to take pictures of elements that relate to the acronym of "TRANS-lighthouses"

To be continued and embedded on the website

V1

<p>Videos</p>	<p>> Video memory: - recorded for the kick-off meeting by partners' teams and edited by Kairós; - to be used on the website for partners' presentation</p> <p>> Other videos to be developed, such as: - documentation of Living Knowledge Labs - democracy labs: webinars, animations - videos produced by youth - institutional video on the project - webinars and conferences</p>	<p><i>Brussels Belgium</i></p> <p><i>ICLD Sweden</i></p> <p><i>Jangada Italy</i></p> <p><i>Cyl Cyprus</i></p>	<p>V1</p>
<p>Database of pictures and videos</p>	<p>> Pictures taken by partners are made available and organised by categories and events.</p> <p>The naming of files include: - what (keywords) - numbering (for similar ones) - who (credit)</p>	<p><i>Observers8_Stage_Fabio_Cyl_ByCML.JPG</i></p>	<p>V1</p>
<p>Database of presentations / participation in events</p>	<p>> Partners are invited to share presentations and participations in events: - as a matter of compilation/reporting - to support the presentations/participations of other colleagues</p>	<p>under development</p>	
<p>Flyer/leaflet /brochure</p>	<p>> To be developed based on institutional profile and messaging > To support partners in networking activities and public events</p>	<p>under development</p>	
<p>Letterhead template</p>	<p>> To be developed based on brand application guidelines</p>	<p>under development</p>	
<p>Digital template of newsletter</p>	<p>> To be developed based on: - brand application guidelines - website design</p>	<p>under development</p>	
<p>Social media templates</p>	<p>> Web postcard > Digital banner > To be developed based on: - brand application guidelines - website design</p>	<p>under development</p>	

Table 14: Communication templates and materials

2.4.3. Communication and interaction adapted to the local contexts

> Work package 6: community-based communication and citizen science

In the framework of work package 6, specific communication and interaction approaches, pathways, channels and tools adapted to the local contexts are also being envisioned.

- Development of a citizen science framework based on reflexive monitoring

Figure 4: Citizen science

Figure 5: Reflexive monitoring process

- Overview of objectives and main approaches

Table 15: Work package 6: overview and main approaches

- Towards NBS communication: principles, strategies, process

Figure 6: Work package 6: communication principles

Figure 7: Work package 6: development of strategies

Figure 8: Work package 6: community-driven processes

> Work package 5: local communication and documentation of the process

- Local communication platforms for engagement and documentation methods

Aim is to clarify ambiguities, integrate knowledge(s) from a variety of stakeholders, to build on local living knowledge, facilitate acceptance of transformations by the local communities and relevant stakeholders, respond to and address voices that are being heard of.

Specifically the task objective is to:

- Enable community-led mapping of natural resources, ecosystem dynamics, infrastructure pressures, and usage of and impact on culturally significant sites.
- Mobilise local actors in order to incorporate local living knowledge into the planning and implementation of NBS.
- Facilitate participatory documentation during the evaluation of the socio-economic viability of a solution, identifying positive or negative perceptions among the community or dialogue on the potential effects that the NBS may have on the landscape and biodiversity.

It is expected that through these activities we can achieve higher levels of local engagement and knowledge communication than typical dissemination approaches. This task will work in tandem with task 3.5, 5.2, 5.3 and 6.5.

Local communication platforms for engagement & documentation methods

Low digital skills documentation process and tools

1. Focus Groups to discuss working over flowchart diagrams with node-link map outputs.
2. Photo-video storyboarding/storywall created by professionals, champions, or through training.
3. Photowalks.
4. Docu-films produced by professionals, champions, or through training and workshops, including semi-structured interviews.

[Documentary film](#) making to document the creation of the NBS pilot and communicate the process and results to mobilise the local communities.

Medium-High digital skills documentation process and tools

1. Serious games (on Actionbound platform) and 3D and multi-sensory documentation of local environments, activities and dynamics by means of multimedia devices (mobile phone camera, voice recorder, sensors) for crowdsourcing of information.
2. Citizen science tools for crowdsourcing / Mobile apps for citizen science for community building around causes to mobilise local groups and stakeholders.

[DARIAH citizen science mobile app](#) for community building around local sites and points of interest.

High digital skills communication and engagement methods and tools

1. Online PPGIS enabled platform for accessing, uploading and sharing georeferenced assets.
2. Visualisation of ecosystem-based adaptation scenarios (impact of climate anomalies or human-technical activities on site, on maps and sketches) created by researchers and disseminated through websites and social media channels.

Translighthouses PPGIS platform prototype.

Visualising timelines of past and future flooding conditions in Pedieos river in Nicosia based on scientific observation and simulated data.

Table 16: Local communication platforms for engagement & documentation methods

- Workflow: research, documentation, creation

Workflow for local communication and documentation of the process

Desk research

<p>Objective → Existing available resources (data, equipment, expertise).</p>	<p>Results → Cultural, historical and background research on the context → Repository of available resources (data, physical, and immaterial)</p>
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Field research

<p>Objective → Collect and produce additional data needed for the analysis of the site/ecosystems/neighbourhood</p>	<p>Results → New data produced through multiple activities (surveys, participatory mapping, etc.) → Spatial basemaps, diagrams and data visualisations.</p>
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Spherical images photogrammetric method to 3D reality capture pilot sites and environments.

Documentation stage

1. Communicate Strategic Visioning values.
2. Documenting and communicating living knowledge.
3. Documenting the co-creation process and strategic development scenarios.
4. Document decision making process including dilemmas dialogue, negotiations in participative budgeting sessions.
5. Document reflective processes – assessing the scenarios.
6. Document creative thinking and mutual understanding.

Stakeholder workshops for strategic visioning of Strovolos pilot using data-driven interactions at the NOUS Strovolos Hub

Open data 3D visualisations of Pedieos river, Nicosia.

Creation stage

1. Abstraction of documented knowledge(s), results, alternative approaches and procedures.
2. Process, convert and visualise data, knowledge(s) and practices.
3. Create workflows, maps and guidelines.
4. Integrate and present in a structured and comprehensive way in the form of a Playbook.

Table 17: Workflow for local communication and documentation of the process

> Work package 4: dissemination and replication of co-governance, and amplifying youth involvement

Work package 4 includes among its objectives to: prepare tools and roadmaps for dissemination and replication; and create curricula content regarding co-governance for just transition.

These objectives are specifically related to task 4.4 and 4.5.

→ Task 4.4 - Roadmaps and tools for dissemination and replication of co-governance

- Dedicated to developing roadmaps for supporting citizens, politicians, technicians, researchers, practitioners and members from local organisations towards transition for models of co-governance and for facilitating enabling environments for co-creation of NBS.
- Transition roadmaps will be produced for the replication of co-governance methodologies:
 - 1) across organisations (public, private, associative and community-based);
 - 2) for policy makers and decision makers; and
 - 3) for citizens & members from local organisations.
- These transition roadmaps will be disseminated through workshops for co-governance, policy briefs, videos and serious gaming, contributing to introducing co-governance criteria in policies and local/regional planning processes.

→ Task 4.5 - Capacity-building to amplify youth involvement in re-inventing institutional governance models towards co-creation of NBS

- Dedicated to research and produce guidelines for the co-creation of NBS by youth, starting by understanding the differences of participation by youth in formal educational contexts and non formal contexts. It will also research how the governance models in educational institutions (high school, vocational education and universities) sustain opportunities and initiatives for participation.
- The results from this research will help students to formulate contributions for re-inventing institutional governance models towards co-creation of NBS.
- The local youth groups activated within the T6.4 will support the task implementation, through the action youth to identify the singularities from their context and to communicate these themes for broader context.
- The task will also introduce NBS co-creation and co-governance content in college disciplines in articulation with scientific partners.

Task 4.4 - Roadmaps and tools for dissemination and replication of co-governance
(inputs from task 5.4)

OUTPUTS	STAKEHOLDERS CATEGORIES		
	Policy makers, Government officials, Local authorities; SMEs; Civil society organisations	Students and educators; Civil society organisations	Citizens - young people
Policy Briefs	GPS territorial roadmap (with virtual interface - LKL) of different models (examples) of co-creation and co-governance NBS		
Videos		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Educational (aimed at children, 4-6 years old; format: storyboard - animated; narrative: revival of the human-nature relationship/ Eco-literacy) - Inspiring (aimed at children and young people, 7-12 years old; format: digital storytelling; narrative: young providers of NBS - bring nature to the table of co-governance/agency of nature itself) 	
Serious games			Aimed at young people, 13-16 years old; narrative: community building => activation of community resources in a synergistic logic/ community appropriation of solutions in a balance between societal challenges and strengthening of biodiversity

Table 18: Roadmaps and tools for dissemination and replication of co-governance

> Work package 3: democracy labs as interfaces between science and policies

Local Democracy Labs complement the Living Knowledges Labs by providing a space for elected representatives in the TRANS-lighthouses pilot cases to explore the *what, how and why* of participatory governance of NBS.

What is participatory governance, how can it work in my existing policy environment, how do I get peers on board with the idea, and what elements of these lighthouses are important for us who govern a pilot to know?

Elected representatives are invited to identify, through a round-table format, a challenge they experience related to the institutionalisation of co-creation and the piloting/establishing of transformative NBS. These are refined and formulated with a view to the conceptual framework and the participatory cultures and governance archetypes identified in tasks 2.1 and 4.2. Researchers from within and beyond the consortium are then recruited as discussants based on their respective competencies in relation to the identified challenges.

The elected representatives are then invited to reconvene and cross-pollinate insights from the labs some months after.

The interactions and challenges identified inform:

- 1) the internal discussions in the political environment of the pilot case;
- 2) the understanding of consortium researchers of political realities and concerns;
- 3) the creation of policy briefs and learning material (learning cases) attempting to boil down research findings according to elected representatives' needs.

Figure 9: Visualisation of the knowledge flow between research and practice in task 3.6

> Work package 2: co-dissemination of living knowledge

In the framework of task 2.6 “Co-dissemination of living knowledge”, the deliverable D2.6 “Guidelines for participatory and inclusive knowledge co-dissemination” focuses on providing guidelines about practices and methods of inclusive and participatory knowledge co-dissemination in NBS co-creation. It aims to provide theory- and practice-oriented guidelines that can guide and inspire the pilot cases developed within the project to engage in processes of knowledge co-creation and co-dissemination with citizens and communities.

Traditional forms of academic knowledge dissemination such as journal articles, books and conferences can often fail to reach the target audiences which are the most affected by the project findings. TRANS-lighthouses project has a particular focus on knowledge co-creation and anchoring NBS in local communities aiming for developing citizen-driven nature-based solutions. Therefore, the deliverable D2.6 focuses on ways to build inclusive and participatory knowledge co-dissemination strategies, working with diverse target groups.

The deliverable distinguishes two interrelated types and objectives of co-dissemination:

- Firstly, inclusive dissemination aimed at making knowledge sharing accessible to diverse groups, stakeholders and beneficiaries.
- Secondly, knowledge co-dissemination approached as a part of broader knowledge co-creation, where citizens play an integral role in co-defining project objectives, research questions and research design, and co-own the knowledge produced in the project.

These objectives are not mutually exclusive, and both of them play an important role in the project timeline. Hence, this deliverable provides guidance on how to work with these interrelated objectives.

The deliverable provides:

i) Discussion of key themes which need to be taken into account in inclusive and participatory knowledge co-dissemination, including

- *Epistemologies of co-production and co-dissemination.* Who creates knowledge and how? (Power relations and epistemological issues in knowledge co-production in Living Knowledge Labs)
- *Collaboration management:* transparency and reflexivity (Transparency about ownership, authorship and joint effort in knowledge co-production and co-dissemination in Living Knowledge Labs)
- *Ethics, risks and consent in co-produced research* (Participatory research involves an often-inherent contradiction between confidentiality and consent due to the dual roles of being participants and co-researchers)

ii) Examples of good practices of inclusive and participatory co-dissemination based on case descriptions

iii) Examples of methods for knowledge co-dissemination

iv) Guidelines and actionable questions to facilitate operationalization of co-dissemination processes in the pilot cases.

2.4.4. Events and publication channels

> Tentative schedule and preliminary selection of events

General schedule of consortium meetings and events					
	In-person consortium meetings	Online consortium meetings	Periodic reviews	Technical visits	Conference
2023	CM #1 - M2 21-23 June 2023 Azores				
		CM#2 - M6 24-25 Oct 2023			
2024	CM #3 - M10 28 Feb - 1 Mar. 2024 Rome				
		CM #4 - M14 June 2024			
	CM #5 - M18 Oct. 2024 Cáceres				
			PR1 - M18-M2 Oct./Dec. 2024	Brussels	
2025		CM #6 - M21 Jan. 2025			
	CM #7 - M25 May -2025 Strovolos				
		CM #8 - M29 Sept. 2025			
			PR2 - M30-M32 Oct./Dec. 2025	Upper Allgau	
2026	CM #9 - M33 Jan. 2026				
					School/Conf. - M37 May 2026 Coimbra-Estarreja-Barcelos
		CM #10 - M41 Sep. 2026			
			Final review		

Table 19: General schedule of consortium meetings and events

Selection/mapping of events	
Types of events	Types of involvement
EU / European Commission events	Application/Invitation for public communications/exhibitions/workshops <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Europe Day - New European Bauhaus Festival - European week of regions and cities - Innovation days
Networking events organised by relevant associations	Application/Invitation for public communications/exhibitions/workshops <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ENoLL - JPI Urban Europe - DUT - Social Economy European Forum - Gathering of the Global Ecovillage Network of Europe (GEN Europe) - Congreso Nacional del Medio Ambiente de España e Iberoamérica CONAMA 2024 - Encuentro de Pueblos y Ciudades por la Sostenibilidad de España CONAMA LOCAL 2025 - New European Bauhaus https://neweuropeanbauhaus.es/en/ - EUGREEN, European Universities Alliance for Sustainability: responsible GRowth, inclusive Education and Environment - 13er Congreso de Compostaje Descentralizado de Composta En Red (Octubre 2024) - "XV Congreso SEAE Producción Ecológica, comprometida con nuestra tierra, gente y alimentos" (Abril 2024) - 39ª edición Biocultura Madrid y 30ª edición Biocultura Barcelona - ENANPARQ 2024 - Encontro da Associação Nacional de Pesquisa e Pós-graduação em Arquitetura e Urbanismo - EUROELECS 2025 - Encontro Latino-americano e Europeu sobre Edificações e Comunidades Sustentáveis
International and referenced conferences	Application/Invitation for public communications <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISA World Congress of Sociology - EURA Conference - NESS - Degrowth - IUFRO - ECSWR - 19th European Congress of Psychology (https://ecp2025.eu/) - World Urban Forum - COP16 Biodiversity 2024 (Colombia) - 2024 Ocean Decade Conference (Barcelona) - COP29 - Baku - COP30 - Brazil
Webinars	Organisation of internal and/or open webinars: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - presentations of horizontal partners and discussions with the consortium members, associated partners and invited participants - dissemination and appropriation of ethics principles, guidelines, procedures and requirements by partners - meetings with ethics board - Webinar Series: NBS, yes? Under what conditions? (TRL - Task force on Community Economies, Transformative Economies and NBS)
Clustering initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Joint events with sibling projects COEVOLVERS and NATURESCAPES - NBS Task Forces gathering EU funded projects - Joint events with sibling project EUGREEN - REAL DEAL https://www.realdeal.eu/about
Local community events of scientific knowledge dissemination	Organised as part of the Living Knowledge Labs activities, in the framework of consortium meetings and technical visits to the sites of the pilot cases
Local dissemination and training workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dissemination of research and guidelines to amplify the involvement of youth and older adults in the co-creation of NBS - In connection with the community-driven communication process based on youth protagonism, and the digital platform of task 6.4, to disseminate more broadly research results, guidelines and activities developed with youth
Democracy labs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Space for local government officers and politicians to meet researchers (task 3.6) - Roundtables with elected representatives

Table 20: Selection/mapping of events

> Preliminary selection of publication channels

Mapping of publication opportunities	
Types of publication	Selection of publications/media
> Open research platforms	- Horizon Results Platform
> Open access publications	- Global Environmental Change (Elsevier)
> International referenced publications (scientific, technical, architect, environmental journals)	- Environment and Behavior (Sage)
	- Environment and Planning A (Sage)
	- Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment (Elsevier)
	- Nature-based solutions (Elsevier)
> Publications with processing charge/fee afforded by the project to grant free access to readers	- Environmental Monitoring and Assessment (Springer)
	- Environment and Planning D: Society and Space (Sage)
	- Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology (Taylor & Francis)
	- Psychosocial Intervention (JCR (Q1), IF 4.8)
	- Social Inclusion (JCR, IF 1.5)
	- Arquitecturas del Sur
	- Revista Nacional de Gerenciamento de Cidades
	- Periódico Técnico e Científico Cidades Verdes
> Specialised magazines/journals	- Centro de Publicaciones del Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico (Spain)
> Specialised blogs and forums	- TED Talks and TED X Talks
>> Featured project presentations	- Partners' pages in local media: Jornal Açoriano Oriental / Page Movimento Kairós
> General media	
>> Media appearances/interview (i.e. TV, radio)	
>> Featured project presentations in local media	

Table 21: Mapping of publication opportunities

2.4.5. Digital strategy

> Internal communication platform and cloud

In their daily collaborative work, the consortium members will make use of online tools and platforms for project management and team communication that are the most commonly used and accessible among partners, in compliance with the data management requirements. Partners are also equipped in their institutions with communications tools that allow online interactions and collaborative work, such as video conferencing.

- **Communication and project management platform: Basecamp**

Basecamp is a web-based project management and collaboration tool. It provides partners with:

- centralised platform for organising tasks and sharing files;
- centralised communication (reducing the need for scattered emails and improving transparency within projects);
- user-friendly interface (use without extensive training).

- **Cloud: Google drive**

As established in the data management plan (v1, deliverable D1.2), data collected/generated will be stored to Google Drive cloud servers using a commercial, non-public licence of Google Workspace that meets privacy and security requirements to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation ([GDPR](#)). It provides partners with:

- unified and real-time collaboration platform: teams can collaborate on documents, spreadsheets, and presentations in real-time;
- file accessibility: from anywhere with an internet connection; offline access also available;
- version control features help track changes and revision;
- centralised administration over user accounts, permissions, and security settings.

- **File findability and accessibility: Naming convention**

As specified in the data management plan (v1, deliverable D1.2), a file naming convention has been agreed and established for all files generated throughout the project. This naming convention defines the rules and abbreviations used for naming and identifying files, thus facilitating their findability and accessibility.

More precisely, the established convention includes the following sequence of components, using underscore as a delimiter between them:

1. Project abbreviation, namely TRL.
2. Work package number, e.g. WP1.
3. Data provider (partner), e.g. ARC, RUC.
4. File type:
 - DATA for data files, datasets,
 - SW for software,
 - DXY for deliverables, as indicated in the grant agreement (where X, Y arithmetic parameters),
 - PLT-XXX for pilots, where XXX is the abbreviation of the pilot case,
 - ASSC-XXX for assessment cases, where XXX is the abbreviation of the assessment case.
5. Date [YYYYMM].
6. Title/description (short free text).
7. Version vXY (where X, Y arithmetic parameters).

> Public repository: Zenodo

As established in the data management plan (v1, deliverable D1.2), deliverables and research results of the project classified as public (i.e. unless restricted by [GDPR](#) or deliverables considered confidential), as well as all scientific publications deriving from it, will be made publicly available with open access:

- at the project's website, and/or
- in the Zenodo trustworthy open repository through the TRANS-lighthouses community¹, under the supported Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence, in addition to the European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE) Community².

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/trans-lighthouses/>

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/openaire/>

> Website

- Domain and hosting

- www.trans-lighthouses.eu is the domain registered by CES-UC.
- It includes a hyphen for readability.
- Hosting is guaranteed by CES-UC until 2 years after the end of the project.
- Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificate was purchased by CES-UC for the address trans-lighthouses.eu in order to encrypt communications between the server and visitors.

- Development stages

- a communication agency has been hired to develop the website (FBA. - Ferrand, Bicker & Associados, www.fba.pt)
- 4-stage development according to project advancements and needs.

Stage 1 Until month 8 Dec. 2023	Stage 2 Until month 18 Oct. 2024	Stage 3 Until month 30 Oct. 2025	Stage 4 Until month 42 Oct. 2026	
Inclusion of basic structure and contents	Complement structure and contents	Complement structure and contents	Adapt structure and contents for the closing of the project	
Beginning of the project	Middle of the project	Middle of the project	End of the project	2 years after end of project
Communication				
	Dissemination			
		Exploitation		

Figure 10: Website - 4-stage development

- Contents development and management

- Contents will be collaboratively developed by the partners of the project TRANS-lighthouses.
- The website will be available in English.
- Communication in the local language of partners and stakeholders from different countries is applicable in the framework of the Living Knowledge Labs of pilot cases and community-based communication, i.e. digital platform and other Educommunication channels, materials and tools developed with Jangada, as part of work package 6.
- Content management system (CMS) provides us with autonomy to maintain and update contents.
- Back office system enables to create profiles for transversal management of the website's content, i.e. system administrators.
- System administrators can create, delete and edit other back office users with the possibility of defining different access permissions.
- In addition to the definition of roles and contributions among consortium members, we will be equipped with a training session on the use of back office and guidelines on good practices in editing/introducing content.

- Structure and functioning

Website main structure/menu - Header					
About	Partners	Lighthouses	News and events	Resources and tools	Contact us
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Objectives & methodology > Work plan > Inspiration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Consortium > Associated partners > Ethics commission > Gender Equality and Diversity focal point > Sibling projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Interactive map > Assessment cases >> Specific pages > Pilot cases >> Specific pages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > News > Calendar > Press room 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Research and innovation > Citizen science > Public repository > Democracy labs > Community-driven communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contact information, newsletter, signup, social media

Table 22: Website main structure/menu - Header

Website functioning across sections and subsections

Sections	Subsections	Functionalities and contents
Home	TRANS-lighthouses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Gallery of images > Key sentences/short introduction/definition > Know more = link to ABOUT > Objectives & methodology
	Ambition and work plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Visual with the acronym > Key sentences/short introduction/definition > Know more = link to ABOUT > Work plan
	Lighthouses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Images of cases and links to dedicated pages > Key sentences/short introduction/definition > Know more = link to LIGHTHOUSES
About	Objectives & methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Clear and concise description of the project. i.e. objectives, methodology/key activities, expected outcomes > Information on the Horizon Europe program and how the project aligns with its goals > Use of visuals and infographics > Downloadable poster, flyer or communication material about the project as a whole
	Work plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Brief description of each work package > Relation between work packages and tasks > Use of visuals and infographics > Visual representation of the project's timeline and milestones > Historical data and progress tracking
	Inspiration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Consortium meetings and visits > Embed interactive contents (Padlet)
Partners	Members of the consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Static map > Categories: academia, cities, civil society organisations > Logo + link to website and contact information for each partner > Role, interests and contribution of each consortium member > Short videos for each team (videos recorded for the kick-off meeting)
	Associated partners / International cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > static map > Plan for international cooperation > Categories: academia, cities, civil society organisations > logo + link to website and contact information for each associated partner > Interests and contribution of each associated partner > Short videos of associated partners, showcasing intercultural diversity
	Ethics advisory board and focal points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Static map > Roles and contribution > Members of the advisory board > Description and channel of ethics management > Local focal points, channels and modalities for reporting > Pictures and short bios > Ethics deliverables, documents, meetings and reports
	Gender Equality and Diversity focal point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Role and contribution > Pictures and short bios of each member
	Sibling projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Brief presentation: COEVOLVERS and NATURESCAPES > Logos + link to website and contact information of coordinators > Common events and productions
Lighthouses	Interactive map	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Showcasing project activities, partner locations, and impact areas > Filters to display specific information by country, region, type of case (assessment, pilot), and lighthouse (urban, rural, forestry, coastal)
	Assessment cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Timeline for cases > Transversal data collection/methods > Assessment-specific pages <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Dedicated pages for each assessment case, highlighting their profile, roles and contributions to the project >> Downloadable posters
	Pilot cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Timeline for cases > Living Knowledge Labs locations > Pilot-specific pages <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Dedicated pages for each pilot case, highlighting their profile, roles and contributions to the project >> Downloadable posters and other resources produced (e.g. videos) >> Information on local initiatives, developments, and stakeholders in each pilot case. >> Link to local platform?

News and events	News	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Blog posts/articles detailing significant milestones, achievements, progress reports > Written by members of the consortium > Filters to display specific information by themes and cases > Regularly updated to keep stakeholders informed about project developments > Link also to the platform that will be managed by the young people, as they will also produce content about the reality and daily life of the pilot cases
	Calendar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Events, workshops, and conferences related to the project > Regularly updated to keep stakeholders informed about project events > Registration and RSVP functionality for participants
	Press room	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Media coverage (e.g. TV and radio appearances, magazines/journals, specialised blogs and forums) > Newsletters (2 per year) > Communications materials/resources in English and translation in local languages > Communications channels and contacts of partners > Embedded social media contents
Resources and tools	Research and innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > All (mosaic and button) + Filters (buttons) > <u>Project's deliverables</u>: complete list, type, leading partner, delivery month, status, dissemination level, restricted access to the deliverables that are not public > <u>Science and practice of NBS</u>: roadmaps, guidelines, frameworks (documents, graphs or interface to access interactive tool), playbook, digital and low-tech tools, videos, technical reports > <u>Webinars and conferences</u>: videos, publications and presentations > <u>Publications</u>: working papers and academic/research publications > <u>Datasets</u> > <u>Living documents</u>: internal, restricted access
	Citizen science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Reflexive monitoring framework > Learning outcomes > NBS communication > Documents, graphs or interface to access interactive tool(s), namely the mapping tool Cyl is developing
	Public repository	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Interface/link Zenodo > Repository for research papers, publications, and reports generated by the project > Easy access to project-related academic content > Link Cordis profile > Link Horizon results platform
	Democracy labs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Policy briefs > Infographics > Roadmaps > Videos/webinars and animated videos > Serious gaming
	Community-driven communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Interface to the digital platform developed by Jangada/Viração (task 6.4) > Resources on Educommunication > Links to dedicated subsites and social media profiles of pilot cases > Repository of media campaigns and videos produced by youth
	Contact us	Contact information
Newsletter sign-up		"Subscribe to TRANS-lighthouses newsletter"
Social media integration		"Follow us on social media": LinkedIn profile, YouTube channel
Footer	Links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > About TRANS-lighthouses; Partners; Lighthouses; News & events; Resources & tools; Contact us; Home > Privacy policy > Subscription to newsletter > Social media icons
	Logos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Partners > EU funding & disclaimer
	Copyright	

Table 23: Website functioning across sections and subsections

- Expected additional features and functionalities

- Privacy policy: clearly communicate the website's privacy policy and data handling practices, quality and GDPR Policy; cookies disclaimer.
- Measures to protect sensitive project data and user information

- Search functionality
- Data visualisation
- Restricted access to some resources
- Accessibility: adoption of web content accessibility guidelines
- User analytics
- Mobile responsiveness
- Feedback mechanism
- Green web hosting: adoption of green web hosting practices

> Social media

The choice of social media platforms depends on the project's goals, target audiences, and communication strategy. A social media strategy and plan content need to be created accordingly, considering also:

- who and how frequently the chosen platforms will be updated;
- unlike the website that serves as a business card and explanation, social media platforms typically require constant updates and investment, some more than others;
- to create and post relevant and adequate/professional contents (visuals and messaging);
- to prepare and implement rigorous and efficient planning for posts, elaboration/design of contents;
- to allocate budget for paid advertising or sponsored content;
- to monitor and moderate interactions;
- content curation;
- compliance with data protection, as well as in terms of intellectual property and data ownership;
- to report regularly on the impact of posts, the evolution of the audience of our social media account/profile, and other social media metrics;
- local groups engaged in the Living Knowledge Labs of pilots may also develop their local social media pages, which will be managed autonomously by them, and may also relay our messages/posts;
- we may also rely on the pages of partners and their institutions.

A preliminary assessment has been conducted to guide the choice of which social media platform we will invest our efforts in. Firstly by mapping possible social media platforms, and, secondly by considering both advantages/benefits and challenges in use and maintenance.

Preliminary assessment for social media strategy and content plan		
Platforms	Decision	Justification
> LinkedIn > Padlet > YouTube	Suitable	- Appropriate target audiences - Manageable - Available resources for investment
> Instagram > ResearchGate > Academia.edu > EurekAlert! > ScienceDaily > The Conversation > SciDev.Net	Needing further assessment	Further assess: - relevance - our management capacity - available resources for investment
> Facebook > X (Twitter) > SlideShare	Not suitable	- No added value - Heavy management and resources needed - Overlapping community-driven communication

Table 24: Preliminary assessment for social media strategy and content plan

2.4.6. Awareness raising and development of guidelines

> Images and messaging

- Build upon existing ethical content guidelines

Updated version of [The Dóchas Code of Conduct on Images and Messages \(2006\)](#) and [The Illustrative Guide to the Dóchas Code of Conduct on Images and Messages \(2014\)](#)

Figure 11: [Dóchas Guide to Ethical Communications 2023](#)

Source: (Dóchas, 2023)

- Core values and commitments

Images and messaging: core values and commitments		
Core values	Meaning	Commitments
Respect for the dignity of people concerned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > appreciating the people and situations > showing consideration for people's privacy and dignity > regarding people as active, valuable and capable agents of change in their own lives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Authentic representation: providing truth and context when portraying the lives of individuals and communities >> Contributor-led stories and locally led content development: putting the people and communities at the centre of communications
Belief in the equality of all people	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > respecting the rights of all people > applying the same standards to everyone > promoting an appreciation of diversity > committing to non-discrimination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Informed consent: all content is obtained with the full understanding, participation and permission of those featured, or in the case of children, of their parents or guardians
Acceptance of the need to promote solidarity, fairness and justice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > <i>Solidarity:</i> using practices, images and messages that promote working together with, rather than on behalf, of communities. > <i>Fairness and justice:</i> highlighting causes, calling for actions to address them and implementing a rights-based approach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Upholding standards and Doing No Harm In planning, gathering and disseminating content - conform to the highest standards and international instruments relating to human rights - commit to the protection of people in vulnerable situations and those with specific needs

Table 25: Images and messaging: core values and commitments
Adapted from Dóchas Guide to Ethical Communications 2023

> Gender

- **Gender Equality and Diversity focal point**

The TRANS-lighthouses' **Gender+ dimension ("plus")** refers to the gender inclusivity perspective, considering non-binary persons as a result of the LGBTIQ+ struggles (Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transexual, Transgender, Travesti, Intersexual, Queer, Asexual, Pansexual + any other), as well as the complex combination of different oppressions and discriminations.

Voice, participation, engagement, accountability and rights regarding gender are key aspects to be taken into account during the project implementation. It is not an "add on" to project work but rather a **central aspect** that was considered since TRANS-lighthouses' conception.

The consortium proposal has largely involved female researchers and it is expected that they will be in a prominent position in leading, managing and coordinating the project. We aim for a **gender balance throughout the consortium**, including the local teams from pilot cases, and throughout the participants in the Living Knowledge(s) Labs.

The project will strive for gender equality in the consortium, echoing the **growing attention and measures to push gender balance in projects funded by the European Commission**. Annexe 5 of our Grant Agreement includes specific rules, namely:

- Art. 14 on gender mainstreaming which states that: *"The beneficiaries must take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action and, where applicable, in line with the gender equality plan. They must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level"*.
- Art. 18 on carrying out the action and addressing access to research infrastructure activities, stating that the beneficiaries must *"promote equal opportunities in advertising the access and take into account the gender dimension when defining the support provided to users"*.

TRANS-lighthouses incorporates a **gender analysis throughout the project**:

- within the development of co-creation tools (WP2 and 6);
- in the assessment of the co-creation (WP3), in the implementation of the pilot cases (WP5);
- as well as co-governance approaches (WP4).

Gender dimension and diversity will be emphasised through a range of theoretical, methodological and technical approaches to be used in the research. Thus, a transnational and multi-scale perspective in itself implies problematizing identities and geographies.

To ensure that gender equality takes priority in all aspects of the project, TRANS-lighthouses will appoint a **Gender Equality and Diversity (GED) focal point**, as devised in task 1.1 and in articulation with task 2.5 with the responsibility of monitoring and ensuring that the project is inclusive, equitable and diverse in the management of its consortium and in its approach and interventions in the project implementation.

- Gender-sensitive communication and gender-responsive approach

Gender-sensitive communication

Communication levels and function: interpersonal, institutional, science
Source: [SUPERA project](#)

Ensuring visibility to all the components of the research and academia community
Source: [SUPERA project](#)

5 areas of gender-sensitive communication
Source: [SUPERA project](#)

Key aspects

- > Importance of having a gender perspective, even in communication activities and in the construction of an imaginary.
- > Sometimes implicit choices, but not so obvious.
- > Images with both men and women, boys and girls.
- > Pictures that do not reinforce stereotypes.
- > Mention both men and women in all discourses.
- > Big responsibility for those involved in communication.
- > Reflect on how to communicate the project, representing women and girls.

Resources

- > Horizon 2020 project SUPERA: [Guidelines for gender-sensitive communication in research and academia](#)
- > Guides for non sexist language used in institutions of the consortium
- > European Institute for Gender Equality: [Toolkit on Gender-sensitive Communication](#)

Table 26: Gender-sensitive communication

Gender-responsive approach in events

Created by Jooyun Lee from Noun Project

Diversity promoted and welcome

- > Making clear that women and men are welcome: "Men and women and broader gender diversity are promoted and welcome"; "if you need any help, clarification or would like to report or give suggestions".
- > Gender neutral language in the conference website and communication materials

Created by Jooyun Lee from Noun Project

International recommendations to coordinators/moderators

- > Equal chances to ask questions
- > Challenge gender stereotypes or prejudice
- > Note of gender-related issues
- > Inform about online survey

Created by Srikrishna Agra from Noun Project

International recommendations to presenters

- > Clarify the relevance of gender balance in relation to the topic presented
- > Illustrations and photos that reflect and value the experience of women/girls and men/boys
- > Information about online survey

Topics and recommendations: partially adapted from ["Topics and Organizing gender-responsive trainings and meetings"](#) - UNESCO Bangkok Office

Table 27: Gender-responsive approach in events and presentations

> Sustainability

Trying to start on the right foot was a concern to design and organise the first in-person collective meeting based on the principles of sustainability and the circular economy. We consider the practices adopted in the kick-off event of TRANS-lighthouses not as a final product or even a recipe, but rather as a foundation from which to build something better.

- Circular events

Keeping in mind the principles of sustainability and the circular economy some measures have been adopted, such as:

Measures based on the principles of sustainability and the circular economy
> Promotion of the event mainly through the media, digital marketing and social networks (local and transnational)
> Programme of the event, partly in hybrid format
> Raising awareness on good environmental practices among partners
> Performance indicators to be refined and improved during the project (social, economic and environmental impacts)
> Use of pre-existing facilities
> Use of the regular installations/equipment, such as canteen of the university (energy reduction)
> Lunch outdoors (energy reduction)
> Purchase in social and solidarity companies that provide local/regional products and traditional gastronomy
> Print content to be reused in all events (specifically, one roll-up to be used in other meetings)
> Use of digital documents and materials (e.g. invitation letters and certificates of attendance)
> Less/no goodies, recycled materials and local tasty gifts
> Waste collection kit (glass-plastic-paper and biowaste)
> Adoption of reusable products and packing in the coffee-break services
> Offer to solidarity institutions the food and materials not used
> Minimise carbon emission on routes/activities during the days of the event, by favouring walking and using collective transport for activities

Table 28: Organisation of events: measures based on the principles of sustainability and the circular economy

- Green web

The development of the project's website constitutes an opportunity to engage with partners to gather their input and requirements. On this occasion, awareness has been raised on green guidelines and 'green host', namely to consider low technology, zero waste, low energy consumption, positive and regenerative impact on nature.³

It involves, for example, to be clear in sizing the website according to the capacity/need for energy consumption that we want to save. Similarly to the times of use of domestic machines, consider low consumption at night and high consumption in the afternoon, and, accordingly, the access to the website may be limited in certain times.

Therefore, TRANS-lighthouses is committed to assessing the extent to which it can introduce these guidelines into the specification definitions and development of its website. In this sense, it should be noted that the energy supply at CES-UC, in Portugal, where the project's website is hosted, is under the responsibility of the University of Coimbra, which also relies on renewable energy, and, consequently, supports "green hosting" measures.⁴⁵

³ As also being explored by the European Commission in relation to measures to improve the energy efficiency and circular economy performance in cloud computing and data centres (<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/green-cloud>).

⁴ <https://www.uc.pt/sustentabilidade/srs/ambiente>

⁵ Moreover, with regard to renewable energy, 61.1% of the electrical energy produced in Portugal in 2021 came from renewable energy sources - for the purposes of the renewable energy sources directive it was 58.4%. From 2016 to 2021, the increase in photovoltaic, biomass and wind technologies were responsible for 9.2% of electricity production from renewable energy sources. In 2021, it appears that Portugal benefited from a 58.4% incorporation of renewables in the

> Accessibility: meetings, work/family reconciliation, events, web

Not all people participate in the same way or under the same circumstances. Each person is different and has different preferences/styles, abilities, opportunities or restrictions. As a matter of promoting fluid meetings, active listening and accessible participation, TRANS-lighthouses' partners have been exchanging practices and concerns that will be further explored throughout the project.

Accessible communication and interaction: practices and concerns

Online video conferencing

Created by IconTrack from Noun Project

> Key aspects on Zoom/video conference fatigue:

- > Somatic and cognitive exhaustion that is caused by the intensive and/or inappropriate use of videoconferencing tools, frequently accompanied by related symptoms such as tiredness, worry, anxiety, burnout, discomfort, and stress, as well as other bodily symptoms such as headaches (Riedl, 2022).
- > Back-to-back video calls: no time for mental, visual, or physical break (while it exist for in-person meetings)
- > Other factors contributing to this fatigue: much more eye-to-eye contact than usual; harder to read nonverbal cues and body language; seeing ourselves in the corner of the screen; less mobility/moving around

> Improve interaction on video calls:

- >> Plan some extra time at the beginning to check in and then focus on working through the agenda
- >> Agenda: prepare, share in advance and follow
- >> Avoid multitasking
- >> Reduce screen stimuli: turn self view; plain backgrounds; turn your camera off when lot of people or majority of screen-shared presentations; reduce size of video call screen to avoid excessive direct eye-contact
- >> Breaks during meetings to re-energise and transition periods between meetings (e.g. get up and stretch your legs, enjoy some fresh air, get some water, coffee, snack, fruit)
- >> Whenever possible shorter calls: people positively engaged rather than distracted or uncomfortable
- >> Mix of communication methods to limit video calls: shared/collaborative documents; clear brief notes and emails to avoid overload of information; instant messenger/Ping; phone calls instead

Assembly signs (*signos asamblearios*)

Created by Robinson Moreno from Noun Project

> Key aspects on promoting fluid meetings, active listening and participation:

- > Not all people participate in the same way or under the same circumstances
- > Each person is different and has different preferences/styles, abilities

> Improve communication in meetings and assemblies:

in favour / against / you are extending / you are repeating yourself / you can't be heard well / I don't see it, but I don't block
Source: https://15mpedia.org/wiki/Signos_asamblearios

Work/family reconciliation

Created by Guilherme Apollinaro from Noun Project

> Key aspects on work/family reconciliation and participation in events:

- > Raised by partners on the occasion of the first general assembly (23 June 2023)
- > Importance of participation in events to the careers, namely present work, get published, networking opportunities
- > However, there are personal costs for travelling abroad and being away during several days, such as family constraints that need to be rearranged and afforded, missing important moments in the life of family members

> How to make events more inclusive for families?

- to be considered for the preparation of events and consortium meetings;
- survey participants⁶ if they might want to bring children and families;
- assess the need for options/measures to be applied case-by-case and to the overall organisation of events;
- e.g. family-friendly locations/destinations with programmes, activities and attractions for children and families; licensed local childcare options; hotels with family suites; participation in one or more social events; arrangements and premises for parenting and caregiving; schedule that enables to pair family vacation with event trip
- options/measures applied to the overall organisation of the event to be eligible and covered by the project's budget allocated to partners
- develop guidelines to welcome attendees such as children, partners, LGBTQIA+ families, pregnant people, relatives with disabilities, caregivers

> Resources/reference documents:

- [Supporting reconciliation of work, family and private life. Good practices](#) / European Institute for Gender Equality
- [Family-friendly workplaces. Overview of policies and initiatives in Europe](#) / European Commission

>> TRANS-lighthouses is committed to assessing the extent to which it can introduce specific measures to facilitate the reconciliation of professional activity and personal/family life, namely in the case of family-friendly events.

electricity sector, which represented the fourth highest rate in the European Union of 27 (<https://rea.apambiente.pt/content/ultimaedicao?language=pt-pt>)

⁶ Resource where we may find some interesting ideas (that have to be adjusted to our case) when designing a possible survey with indicators to know more about the participants necessities but also to evaluate the implementation of reconciliation measures: <https://www.unicef.org/mongolia/media/3666/file/Family-friendly%20policies.pdf>

<p>Accessible events</p> <p><small>Created by Christine Goad from Noun Project</small></p>	<p>> Key aspects/features on accessibility:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > It is important to think about accessibility for those who will present at the event and also for those who will attend > Ask openly before the event what is necessary to serve each participant > For a long event you need to think about accessible accommodation > Event presentations must be sent to the organiser. This practice makes it much easier for sign language translators > Activate captions on any video used in the presentation > Have sign language interpreters > Food: Clearly indicate allergens and gluten-free, vegan, vegetarian, or other options. > Consider those who may be in a wheelchair or have other mobility impairments > Consider access and space for service dogs > Encourage hourly breaks > Accessible parking > Is the event location close to public transport? Is the public transport that serves this route accessible? > Accessible bathrooms > Are the lights adjustable so you can control the brightness of the room? Good lighting helps people with hearing impairments read lips or communicate using sign language. <p>>> TRANS-lighthouses is committed to assessing the extent to which it can introduce specific measures to facilitate accessibility to events.</p>
<p>Accessible website</p> <p><small>Created by Integrom from Noun Project</small></p>	<p>> Key aspects/features on accessibility:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) colour and contrast between figures/text and background 2) have voice recognition 3) texts that can be recognized and read by text reader tools⁷ 4) have a clean and clear design, as simple as possible 5) have a space (or an email contact) for people with disabilities to report accessibility problems 6) the website must be tested by people with different types of disabilities 7) free tool for a type of virtual assistant that uses sign language on websites 8) have contrast options and letter changes 9) make navigation as simple as possible 10) fonts must be readable and accessible 11) being able to access with quality on your cell phone <p>> Web Content Accessibility Guidelines - https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/wcag/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Following these guidelines will make content more accessible to a wider range of people with disabilities, including accommodations for blindness and low vision, deafness and hearing loss, limited movement, speech disabilities, photosensitivity, and combinations of these, and some accommodation for learning disabilities and cognitive limitations - But will not address every user's need for people with these disabilities. - These guidelines address accessibility of web content on desktops, laptops, tablets, and mobile devices. - Following these guidelines will also often make web content more usable to users in general. <p>>> TRANS-lighthouses is committed to assessing the extent to which it can introduce these guidelines into the specification definitions and development of its website.</p>

Table 29: Accessible communication and interaction: practices and concerns

⁷ In this matter of the text, it is necessary to be very careful because it is not only the format that may or may not be compatible with screen reader programs, the words may not be read correctly. Even though today there are software options that read, for example, "tod@s" "todxs", many people still use softwares that cannot read this type of supposedly accessible language.

3. Monitoring and evaluation

In addition to defining indicators that allow us to evaluate the effectiveness of our communication, dissemination and exploration efforts, the project also incorporates a reflexive monitoring framework, as well as measurement and assessment frameworks and referenced guidelines for monitoring and evaluation.

3.1. Reflexive monitoring

Reflexive monitoring, as set out in the framework of task 6.1, applies across work packages, including communication, dissemination and exploitation of results, which are also transversally operationalised. It requires finding time for reflection in the framework of work packages' activities. Enabling a learning environment provides:

- insight into the progress of the project in real time;
- assessment of processes of learning-by-doing and doing-by-learning in terms of goals achievement;
- learning outcomes.

Figure 12: Reflexive monitoring: find time for reflection and enable a learning environment

3.2. Revision and updates

Learning outcomes emerging from reflexive monitoring will feed into two updates of the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan, tools, materials and activities, making the most of internal communication expertise and resources to document the project implementation. Therefore, the second and third versions (deliverables D1.7 and D1.9) will constitute updates and reports on the implementation of the plan that defines strategies, activities and expected results according to different target audiences, corresponding messages and tools. These reports are respectively expected to be delivered at month 30 and month 40 of the project.

Moreover, as aforementioned, the communication materials are produced in consultation with the participants of work package 6 dedicated to community-based communication and citizen science. In this framework, task 1.5 and work package 6 have joined efforts and launched a communications survey to know the communication capabilities and tools/channels that each partner manages. The survey will be followed by a workshop with key communication persons identified through the survey, which is aimed at advancing the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan in strategic and operational terms.

This first communications survey was organised in 5 blocks of questions to assess objectives, environment and communicative capacity of partners, as shown in the table below and further detailed in Annex 1. The results of the survey are under compilation and analysis in preparation of the assessment/review workshop to be conducted with the key communication persons.

Overview of communications survey 1 (Sep. 2023)

1. Contribution, doubt, or disagreement on communication goals

- > Communication goals (task 1.5)
- > Objectives of work package 6
- > Another relevant communication objective to consider

2. Partners' communication environment

- > Limitations to the use of mass media or traditional channels
- > Media coverage area
- > Style and scope of the usual communication
- > Involvement culture of the private sector and civil society
- > Political dynamics
- > Cultural characteristics and diversity
- > Role and capacity of civil society
- > Existing related development efforts and communication campaigns

3. Communicative capacity of the partners' organisation/entity

- > Capacity for dissemination dissemination
- > Communication officer
- > Channels used to communicate, inform, disseminate, calls
- > Networks for dissemination

4. KPIs for measuring and evaluate strategic performance of actions

- > Use of indicators:
 - visibility
 - engagement
 - conversion
 - sentiment
 - other relevant KPIs

5. Communication contacts and channels

- Communicational interface with the WP6 and Task 1.5
- Communication channels of the partners' organisation/entity

Table 30: Overview of communications survey 1 (Sep. 2023)

This process will kick-start the review and further development of the plan, since the information shared is essential to be able to carry out an adapted plan, and develop corresponding tools and materials. That is to say, making accessible, concrete, actionable and meaningful preliminary devised measures and, consequently, review and update them as the project progresses, ensuring flexibility to adapt to changing circumstances.

Therefore, the group of "communications contact persons" constitute a communicational interface with task 1.5 and WP6 who will support:

- the assessment of communication objectives, as well as the environment and communicative capacity of partners;
- the refinement of key performance indicators (KPI) and key exploitable results (KER).

3.3. Key performance indicators and preliminary identification of key exploitable results

Project's key results	Activities	Indicators / KPI	2023	2024	2025	2026	> Comments & updates /
							>> Key exploitable results / KER (preliminary identification) ⁸
1. The project's successful implementation → Awareness about activities and results	Definition of communication policy, procedures and objectives by the steering committee	- 1 communication, dissemination and exploitation plan	X				
		- 2 updated versions of the plan, including reporting on implementation			X	X	
		- 1 kick-off event	X				> June 2023, Azores
		- 1 international conference/summer school				X	>> Academic and practitioner utilisation (via publications) in further research and innovation actions >> Training materials can be used by partners and stakeholders to organise same or similar programme
		- 1 closing event				X	
		- 3 public communications/exhibitions/workshops in EC events		X	X	X	
		- 3 public communications/sessions/workshops in networking events		X	X	X	
		- 6 participations of partners in national, regional and international events		X	X	X	
		- 1 project brand and application guidelines	X				
	Design of communication tools to support the development of communication materials	- 1 dissemination package with communication templates and materials	X	X	X	X	> Complemented along project
		- 1 project website / 4-stage development	X	X	X	X	
		- 1 digital template of newsletter	X	X			
		- 2 social media accounts created	X	X			
		- 1 database with images, news and communication and dissemination inputs and metrics	X	X	X	X	> Complemented along project
	Development of communication materials	- 1 fact sheet/project overview, updated at least once, translated in local languages	X	X	X	X	> Update and translation along project
		- 1 leaflet/flyer/brochure, updated at least once, translated in local languages		X	X	X	> Update and translation along project
		- 1 poster about the project, updated at least once, translated in local language	X	X	X	X	> Update and translation along project
		- 8 posters of pilot cases, 10 posters of assessment cases, updated at least once, translated in local languages	X	X	X	X	> Update and translation along project >> Development into implementation stories >> Potential for future projects and/or organisations to write up their experiences using this template >> Reference materials for training purposes
		- 2 blog posts in the project website per partner during the lifetime of the project		X	X	X	
		- 200 unique visitors to the website per year		X	X	X	> Evolving reach
		- 100 downloads for public deliverables during the lifetime of the project		X	X	X	

⁸ The preliminary identification of key exploitable results will be updated during the project, e.g. some might merge or be defined in a different way, and new KERs might be also considered.

		- 2 newsletters per year		X	X	X	
		- 500 mailing list subscribers		X	X	X	> Evolving reach
		- 5 press releases in English	X	X	X	X	
		- at least 1 post in social media account per month		X	X	X	
		- 300 followers in social media account		X	X	X	> Evolving reach
		- 1 institutional video, translated in local languages			X	X	>> Reference material for training purposes
	Divulgence of the project in the websites and newsletters of international networks and stakeholders, traditional media	- 4 media appearances (i.e. TV, radio)		X	X	X	
		- 3 publications in specialised magazines/journals		X	X	X	
		- 5 featured project presentations in specialised blogs and forums		X	X	X	
	Development of interactions among consortium members, as well as tools and platforms for project management and team communication	- monthly online meetings of the steering committee	X	X	X	X	
		- 10 consortium meetings (in-person/online) and general assemblies	X	X	X	X	
		- 3 technical visits to pilot/assessment cases		X	X	X	
		- 2 monitoring reports per year by work package leaders	X	X	X	X	
		- 1 set of guidelines on project's workflow and standard quality procedures		X	X	X	>> Methodological resources that can support awareness raising and development of guidelines of partners, stakeholders and other research and innovation actions, appropriate action and the realisation of good practices (e.g. ethics, gender, sustainability, accessibility)
		- 1 Gender Equality and Diversity (GED) focal point appointed, working with the steering committee		X	X	X	
		- 1 internal communication platform	X	X	X	X	
		- 1 cloud storage space		X	X	X	
2. Community of practice → Plurality of models, strategies and findings showcased from a diversity of contexts	Knowledge sharing and synergies building among partners, and in the framework of clustering activities with other projects	- 2 internal and/or open webinars per year, with presentations of horizontal partners and discussions with the members of the consortium, associated partners and invited participants		X	X	X	
		- 1 clustering with projects/liaison with networks (starting from EU funded projects)		X	X	X	>> NBS Task forces collaboration in the form of joint messaging, events and communications campaigns to ensure visibility
		- 2 collaborations with sibling projects		X	X	X	>> Joint communication and dissemination activities, scientific exchange
	Involving associated partners in a community of practice	- 2 webinars per year	X	X	X	X	
		- 1 consortium event and/or technical visit		X	X	X	
		- 2 reports based on the compilation and analysis on knowledge sharing and synergies building		X		X	
		- 1 publication with non-European countries, based on North-South cross comparison				X	>> Academic and practitioner utilisation in research and innovation actions

3. Expanded conceptual framework and assessment for NBS	Scientific dissemination of expanded conceptual framework and assessment for NBS in publications & conferences	- 4 papers in international referenced publications			X	X	>> Academic and practitioner utilisation in research and innovation actions
		- 6 presentations and publications with international and referenced conferences		X	X	X	>> Academic and practitioner utilisation in research and innovation actions
→ Living knowledge to be co-disseminated	Inclusive knowledge and practice dissemination, by means of unconventional initiatives of knowledge sharing, such as local community events, local media, and networks	- 8 local community events of scientific knowledge dissemination in Living Knowledge Labs			X	X	
		- 6 featured project presentations in local media	X	X	X	X	
		- 3 clustering and liaison with networks		X	X	X	>> Joint messaging, events and communications campaigns to ensure visibility.
4. Science for citizens and policy makers	Results are shared and made accessible throughout the research process by means of internal living documents	- 2 internal living documents to inform the project ongoing activities and disseminate internally among partners and local stakeholders intermediates results		X	X		>> Joint messaging, events and communications campaigns to ensure visibility.
		- translation of the primary English version into local languages by the respective consortium partners			X	X	>> Joint messaging, events and communications campaigns to ensure visibility.
	Democracy labs	- 3 democracy labs		X	X	X	
	- 3 policy briefs, infographics, videos and serious gaming produced to provide guidance for co-governance		X	X	X	>> Actionable knowledge for informed decision-making and tailored policies >> Training materials can be used by partners and stakeholders to support appropriate action and the realisation of good practices	
	- 5 learning cases/dilemmas to be created with local governments and civil society organisations		X	X	X	>> Actionable knowledge for informed decision-making and tailored policies >> Training materials can be used by partners and stakeholders to support appropriate action and the realisation of good practices	
- 2 animated videos on Lab Democracy for NBS		X	X	X	>> Actionable knowledge for informed decision-making and tailored policies >> Training materials can be used by partners and stakeholders to support appropriate action and the realisation of good practices		
5. Co-governance innovations towards co-creation of NBS	Production of transition roadmaps	- 3 roadmaps disseminated through workshops for co-governance, policy briefs, videos and serious gaming			X	X	>> Actionable knowledge for informed decision-making and tailored policies >> Training materials can be used by partners and stakeholders to support appropriate action and the realisation of good practices
	Development of research and guidelines to amplify the involvement of youth and older adults in the co-creation of NBS	- 8 dissemination and training workshops, one per pilot		X	X		
		- 8 videos, one per pilot, produced by youth			X	X	>> Joint messaging, events and communications campaigns to ensure visibility. >> Development into implementation stories >> Reference material for training purposes
→ Replication and amplification		- 1 pilot introduction of NBS co-creation and co-governance content in college disciplines				X	>> Training materials can be used by partners and stakeholders to support appropriate action and the realisation of good practices
6. Living Knowledge(s) Labs	The communication strategies for social mobilisation and citizen engagement are devised with the communities and participants, supported by frameworks, guidelines and tools developed in WP6	- 8 Living Knowledge Labs established and documented		X	X	X	
		- 4 NBS participatory budgeting processes organised to select locally the NBS			X	X	
		- 8 sets of graphic and text material (one per pilot) for a diffused awareness about the aims of the specific pilot		X	X	X	
		- 8 adaptations of the project's communication materials by teams for local use and dissemination		X	X	X	

	The documentation of the overall design and implementation process of the pilot cases applies a cross-medial approach	- 1 playbook co-produced with the participants of the 8 pilot cases			X	X	>> Joint messaging, events and communications campaigns to ensure visibility. >> Development into implementation stories >> Reference material for training purposes
		- 1 database with labs' images, news and other relevant communication and dissemination inputs and metrics		X	X	X	
7. Citizen science global framework for NBS → Community-based communication and assessment	Mobilisation of citizens' local knowledges and development of trust	- 1 living global framework of citizen science for NBS			X	X	>> Based on citizen science results and resources coming from different work packages, illustrates examples covering relevant practice areas, and motivates the adoption of reflexive monitoring to advance the NBS science and practice
		- 1 portfolio of participatory methods			X	X	>> Actionable knowledge based on methodology and tools >> Development into implementation stories >> Reference material for training purposes
		- 1 digital platform co-created with youth inhabitants of the pilot cases, including 8 subsites			X	X	>> Educommunication >> Development into implementation stories >> Reference material for training purposes
		- 1 social media account followed by a diversity of local stakeholders and citizens in each lab			X	X	
		- 1 media campaign developed with youth in each lab			X	X	>> Joint messaging, events and communications campaigns to ensure visibility.
	Exploration of data usability and tools (contexts and profiles):	- 1 data usability demonstrator			X		>> Actionable knowledge based on methodology and tools >> Development into implementation stories >> Reference material for training purposes
		- 1 report on digital and low-tech tools building on how these tools have been explored in the pilot cases to support participatory assessment and embedded in the implementation of NBS				X	
8. Research data and knowledge → Accessibility, preservation and ethics compliance	Compliance with open access principles	- 1 data management plan and 1 communication, dissemination and exploitation plan integrating principles	X		X	X	
		- 20 resources available on the project's website to be downloaded with no restrictions		X	X	X	>> Academic and practitioner utilisation in further research and innovation actions
		- 1 Zenodo TRANS-lighthouses community	X	X	X	X	>> Academic and practitioner utilisation in further research and innovation actions
		- 3 publications on open research platforms, including the Horizon Results Platform		X	X	X	>> Academic and practitioner utilisation in further research and innovation actions
		- 1 publication with processing charge/fee afforded by the project to grant free access to readers			X	X	>> Academic and practitioner utilisation in further research and innovation actions
	Management and protection:	- 1 consortium agreement with detailed regulations regarding the protection and exploitation of project results		X			
		- 1 data management plan, updating and reporting on its implementation twice until the end of the project	X		X	X	
	Elaboration and application of ethics requirements	- 4 ethics deliverables under work package 7	X	X	X	X	
- 1 external independent ethics advisor/board		X	X	X	X		
- 1 guide on research ethics and inclusive participation for NBS			X			>> Research methodology/methods that can be exploited in various research and innovation actions	

	- activation of 8 focal points and local ethics channels, including modalities for reporting		X	X	X	
	- 2 meetings of the consortium with the external independent ethics advisor/board		X	X	X	
	- 2 webinars for the dissemination and appropriation of ethics principles, guidelines, procedures, requirements		X	X		
	- translation of the primary English version of ethics documents into local languages by respective consortium partners		X	X	X	>> Research methodology/methods that can be exploited in various research and innovation actions, but tailored to needs and target groups

Table 31: Indicators for monitoring and evaluation (KPI) and identification of exploitable results (KER)

3.4. Monitoring tools

TRANS-lighthouses project manager has developed tracking tools to support the collection of data about dissemination and communication activities for reporting purposes. These are collaborative tools which will enable all partners to:

- be aware of their obligations in relation to communication and dissemination;
- inform and keep track of communication and dissemination activities and outcomes;
- support the consortium internal reporting, as well as to report to the funding authority.

As detailed in the table below, these tools cover:

- consortium channels;
- dissemination reporting;
- communication reporting;
- press and media.

MONITORING TOOLS

Consortium channels

Dissemination reporting

Communication reporting

Press and media

Table 32: Monitoring tools

3.5. Assessment frameworks

3.5.1. Gender: events and survey

We present below an initial assessment framework, around six main topics⁹, to be tested and fine-tuned according to what we were able to monitor before, during and after events. This framework will be enriched with recommendations, indicators and assessments emerging from our work together.

Assessment framework - Gender	
1 Gender balance in the composition of sessions coordination, presenters and participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Balance of women/men (organising/coordinating, invited, attending) - Balance in terms of positions (senior men/women; junior men/women)
2 Composition of topics and entrees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relevance of the topics to the lives of women and men - Illustrations and photos in the materials
3 Accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Safe travelling to the event venue - Disability-accessible toilet facilities - Separate toilet for men and women - Prayer spaces - Child care - Timing according to parents responsibilities - Affordability/funding for participation
4 Management and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring gender responsiveness in preparation and delivery stages - Making clear that women and men are welcome - Gender neutral language
5 Facilitation, moderation, chair and note-taking of sessions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Balance of women/men invited - Gender awareness and responsiveness
6 Monitoring & evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Survey: gender of participants; relevance of the presentations and discussions for gender diversity; according to gender ID, assess if the needs and expectations of men/women/other genders were met; evaluation of gender sensitiveness of the event in terms of equal opportunities to present/talk/discuss; suitability of the event in terms of adequate facilities, friendly communication and support for different genders - Mechanism to replicate lessons learned regarding gender responsiveness by the partners' organisations - Compilation of gender-related issues that were raised during discussions and that arose during organisation or running of event

Table 33: Assessment framework - Gender

Template of online post-event survey - Gender					
I. To what extent did the event fulfil the following objectives in relation to gender	1	2	3	4	5
- Openness for all genders to submit contributions to the program					
- Balanced representation of genders among the participants of the event					
- Representative coverage in the programme of sessions of different gender issues in relation to nature-based solutions for inclusive communities					
- Discussions during main and parallel sessions inclusive for all genders					
- Balanced representation of genders amongst session coordinators/rapporteurs					
- New insights were presented concerning gender aspect in relation to citizen engagement in nature-based solutions					
- Overall, the event was an equal opportunity for all genders to participate and contribute					
II. Your experiences around gender issues at the event	1	2	3	4	5
- I experienced concrete examples of gender discrimination					
- I observed gender bias in one or more of the presentations					
- I enjoyed specific participant contributions that unprogrammed highlighted important gender issue					

1. Not at all; 2. To a low extent; 3. To a medium extent; 4. To a high extent; 5. Don't know

Table 34: Template of online post-event survey - Gender

⁹ The topics are partially adapted from: https://bangkok.unesco.org/sites/default/files/assets/article/Education/publications/GENIA2019/19_Dec_GENIA_Toolkit_25.pdf

3.5.2. Sustainability: events and green web

We present below an initial framework to be tested and fine-tuned according to what we were able to monitor before, during and after events. This framework will be enriched with recommendations, indicators and assessments emerging from our work together.

> Events

Assessment framework - Sustainability		
Impact & Indicators	Measurement	Results
I. Environmental impact		
Number of plastic bottles collected	Unity	
Total of reused papers	Kg	
Total of meals repurposed	Kg	
Total bio waste collected	Kg	
Estimation - by foot or cycle distances	Km	
Total of reused glass bottles	Unity	
% of collective buildings used	%	
% of outdoor spaces used	%	
Total of collective transports used (ratio by: number of passengers vs n. of participants) / Car-pooling (ratio by: number of vehicles vs number of passengers).	Unity	
Format adopted to ensure inclusive participation and to reduce travelling	Strategy	
Total of resources dematerialized, including certificates, programmes and others.	Unity	
Total of the disposable utensils used (the goal is zero)	Unity	
Total of gifts and merchandising in recycled material or reusable	Unity	
II. Economic impact		
Expenses incurred with/for local NBS during the event	€	
Total of expenses incurred with local social enterprises	€	
Total of expenses incurred with local companies (small and micro)	€	
III. Social impact		
Number of social enterprises and social projects included in the event	Unity	
Number of students participating in the event implementation (youth engagement)	Number	

Table 35: Assessment framework - Sustainability

> Green web

- Information from the European Union on green guidelines and 'green host': <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/green-cloud>
- Green Web Hosting Certification Types: the two main types of certifications related to green web hosting are Renewable Energy Certificates (REC) for anyone, and Carbon Offset Certificates (VER) for large companies with a database centre.
- Information on websites using green host in the world: <https://www.thegreenwebfoundation.org>
- Example of web hosted in a green host: <https://store.mosaert.com/ethics/green-web>
- Example on low tech activism and website design: <https://solar.lowtechmagazine.com/2023/06/rebuilding-a-solar-powered-website>

3.5.3. Accessibility: events and web

> References for checking accessibility

- European Accessibility Act <https://www.inclusion-europe.eu/european-accessibility-act/>

- Accessibility in events
https://accessibleportugal.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/acessibilidade-eventos_web.pdf
- Public (free) tool used to check the accessibility of websites:
<https://accessmonitor.acessibilidade.gov.pt/>
- Website that is considered an accessibility reference in Portugal:
<https://www.dges.gov.pt/pt>
- What many sites don't have: alternative text on all images

4. Responsible partners and resources

Responsible partners and resources			
Role/Key partners involved	Responsibilities	Resources	
<p>> Project coordinator</p> <p>>> CES-UC</p>	<p>> Coordination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - coordination of communication activities - liaison with partners for content and updates - oversight of dissemination and exploitation efforts - collaboration with partners for consortium and outreach events, exploitation activities <p>> Media outreach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Press releases, articles, and interviews - Drafting and distribution (collaborative process with partners) <p>> Multimedia content</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - videos and webinars (together with specific tasks outputs) - content creation and production (supported by professional services) - platforms for hosting and dissemination 	<p>> Communication materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - templates, fact sheet/project overview, leaflet/flyer, posters, newsletter (supported by professional services) - content creation and production (collaborative process with WP6) <p>> Website (project) [task 1.5]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - design and maintenance - updates and content management (collaborative process with partners) <p>> Social media (supported by professional services)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LinkedIn, Padlet, YouTube channel - planning: who, how, what, when - content creation, posting and curation - allocate budget for paid advertising or sponsored content - monitor and moderate interactions - compliance with data protection, intellectual property, data ownership - reporting on impact, evolution audience, account/profile, metrics 	<p>>> Other goods and services: allocation of resources to specific activities, channels, tools and materials</p> <p>>> Data base</p> <p>>> Communications agency (EBA)</p> <p>>> Project management office</p> <p>>> Events, communication and image office</p> <p>>> Information technology office</p>
<p>> Steering committee</p> <p>>> CES-UC, RUC, TUM, Cyl, Uni. Eiffel.-CNRS, Athena RC</p>	<p>> Coordination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - collaboratively responsible for the framing and update of the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan, tools, materials and activities - overall responsibility for plan implementation - collaboration with partners for consortium and outreach events, exploitation activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - making the most of internal communication expertise and resources - refinement of KPIs and identification of KERs - liaison with partners for content and updates - transversal operationalisation across key results and WPs 	<p>>> Monthly steering committee meetings</p> <p>>> WPs reporting and planning</p> <p>>> Application to Horizon results Booster</p>
<p>> WP6 participants</p> <p>>> <i>Dedicated to community-based communication and citizen science</i></p> <p>>> <i>Communication and interaction approaches, pathways, channels and tools adapted to local contexts</i></p>	<p>> Coordination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - communications survey (T1.5 and WP6) - assess communication capabilities/tools/channels of partners - accessible, concrete, actionable and meaningful measures - review and update, ensuring flexibility <p>> Citizen science: setting-up and coordinating reflexive monitoring [T6.1]</p> <p>> Development of resources for action</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - social mobilisation [T6.2] - citizen engagement [T6.2] - NBS communication [T6.2] - involvement of people with disabilities [task 6.2] [task 6.3] - portfolio of participatory methods [T6.3] - educommunication [T6.4] - digital and low tech tools [T6.5] 	<p>> Communication materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - in the framework of T1.5, communication materials are produced in consultation with the participants of WP6 - format and content - aiming at appropriation and adaptation by teams for local use - fine tuning key messages <p>> Website (digital platform, subsites), Social media, Multimedia content [T6.4]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to support the activities of community communication of NBS with youth - including dedicated subsites for each pilot cases - linked to the development of social media and media campaigns <p>> Digital and low tech tools building [T6.5]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to support participatory assessment and data usability - research and assessment results accessible, relevant to audiences and users 	<p>>> Dedicated tasks and specific outputs of WP6, with corresponding allocated budgets</p> <p>>> Other goods and services</p> <p>>> Collaborative and iterative dynamic with WP5 and WP4 (namely in the development of resources for action)</p>

<p>> Communications contact persons</p> <p>>> <i>Identified by each partner</i></p>	<p>> Coordination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - contact persons identified in communications survey - communicational interface with Task 1.5 and WP6 - support assessment of objectives, environment and communicative capacity of partners - participation in assessment/review workshop - workshop aimed at advancing the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan - support refinement of KPIs and KERs 	<p>> Liaison with the channels and tools of each partner</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - distribute/make available Communication materials - relay messages of Website (pages of partners and their institutions) - relay messages of Social media (pages of partners and their institutions) - relay press releases, articles, and interviews for Media outreach (communication office of partners, mailing lists) - internal sharing of what is happening in the field, with each partner, to celebrate achievements, inspire others, and ask for inspiration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Contact list >> Data base >> Surveys and workshops organised by T1.5 and WP6 >> Take advantage of consortium meetings and reflexive monitoring process
<p>> Local partners</p> <p>>> Pilot cases</p> <p><i>Brussels, Rome, Strovolos, Estarreja, Barcelos, Azores, Regenerative farming network, Cáceres</i></p>	<p>> Living Knowledge Labs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - outreach events - collaboration with local stakeholders / exploitation activities - translation of communication materials into local languages provided by the respective consortium partners (Portugal, Denmark, Cyprus, Belgium, Italy, Spain) - targeting local stakeholders, communities, citizens - update of posters 	<p>>> Communication materials >> Events >> Website >> Social media >> Multimedia content >> Media outreach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - videos and webinars (together with specific tasks outputs) - content creation and production, i.e. documentation of the overall design and implementation process of the pilot cases (cross-medial approach) - playbook co-produced with the participants of the 8 pilot cases - subsites and local social media pages managed autonomously - relay the project's messages/posts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Living Knowledge Labs >> Digital platform, subsites >> Database >> Dedicated tasks and specific outputs of WP5, allocated budgets >> Other goods and services
<p>KPIs PILOT CASES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8 posters of pilot cases, updated at least once, translated in local languages - 8 local community events of scientific knowledge dissemination in Living Knowledge Labs - 6 featured project presentations in local media - 3 policy briefs, infographics, videos and serious gaming produced to provide guidance for co-governance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 5 learning cases/dilemmas to be created with local governments and civil society organisations - 2 animated videos on Lab Democracy for NB - 8 dissemination and training workshops, one per pilot - 8 videos, one per pilot, produced by youth - 1 media campaign developed with youth in each lab 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Consortium meetings and technical visits
<p>> Local partners</p> <p>>> Assessment cases</p> <p><i>Brussels, Bologna, Troodos, Estarreja, Barcelos, Lagoa, Regenerative farming network, Madrid, Upper Allgäu, Moisdon-la-Rivière</i></p>	<p>> Communication materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - translation into local languages will be provided by the respective consortium partners (Portugal, Denmark, Germany, Cyprus, France, Belgium, Italy, Spain) - update of posters 	<p>> Events, Media outreach and Social media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - outreach events - exploitation activities - dissemination targeting local stakeholders, communities, citizens - collaboration with local stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Data base >> Dedicated tasks and specific outputs of WP3, allocated budgets >> Other goods and services >> Consortium meetings and technical visits
<p>SPECIFIC KPIs ASSESSMENT CASES</p>	<p><i>10 posters of assessment cases, updated at least once, translated in local languages</i></p>		
<p>> Local partners</p> <p>>> Associated partners</p> <p><i>Non-EU based organisations: Chile, Argentina, Brazil, India, USA, Tanzania, Kenya</i></p>	<p>> Communication materials</p> <p>translation of communication materials into local languages provided by the respective associated partners (Chile, Argentina, Brazil, India, USA, Tanzania, Kenya)</p>	<p>> Events, Media outreach and Social media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - outreach events - exploitation activities - dissemination targeting local stakeholders, communities, citizens - collaboration with local stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Dedicated task 1.3 and specific outputs, allocated budget >> Other goods and services
<p>SPECIFIC KPIs ASSOCIATED PARTNERS</p>	<p>Participation in activities of the work plan:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - in at least 2 webinars per year - in at least 1 technical visit and/or 1 consortium event 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 reports based on the compilation and analysis on knowledge sharing and synergies building - at least 1 publication with non-European countries, based on North-South cross comparison 	

<p>> All partners</p> <p>>> <i>Art. 17 Grant Agreement</i></p> <p>>> <i>Transversal operationalisation</i></p> <p>>> <i>Monitoring, inform and share</i></p>	<p>> Communication materials [database]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - about project based on project's templates and materials - promote action and results, targeted information, multiple audiences - must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag - communication or dissemination activity must indicate disclaimer translated into local languages where appropriate <p>> Transversal operationalisation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - activities and outputs across work packages/project's key results - publications in journals/magazines [Monitoring/Inform/Share] - presentations in conferences and in networking events [Monitoring/Inform/Share] - content creation, production, videos, webinars (specific tasks outputs) - outreach events [Monitoring/Inform/Share] - exploitation activities 	<p>> Website</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - contributions to relevant sections of the project's website - at least 2 blog posts in the website per partner during the lifetime of project - the project may rely on the pages of partners and their institutions <p>> Social media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - contributions to posts - the project may rely on the pages of partners and their institutions <p>> Media outreach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - interviews - connections with journalists and networks - available distribution lists 	<p>>> Database</p> <p>>> Dedicated tasks and specific outputs, with corresponding allocated budgets</p> <p>>> Other goods and services</p> <p>>> Consortium meetings and technical visits</p> <p>>> Making the most of internal communication expertise and resources</p>
<p>GENERAL KPIs for ALL PARTNERS</p>	<p>General Communication KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 public communications/exhibitions/workshops in EC events - 3 public communications/sessions/workshops in networking events - 2 blog posts in the project website per partner during the lifetime of the project - 5 press releases in English - 1 institutional video, translated in local languages - 4 media appearances (i.e. TV, radio) - 2 webinars per year (community of practice) 	<p>General Dissemination KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 6 participations of partners in national, regional and international events - 6 presentations and publications with international and referenced conferences <p>General Publication KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 publications in specialised magazines/journals - 5 featured project presentations in specialised blogs and forums - 1 publication with non-European countries, based on North-South cross comparison - 4 papers in international referenced publications 	

Table 36: Responsible partners and resources

5. Risk assessment, ethics compliance, and data privacy

5.1. Risk assessment

5.1.1. General risks in international and interdisciplinary projects

When coordinating a European project with partners from various countries and diverse backgrounds, such as academia, NGOs, municipalities, etc., one of the significant risks is the potential lack of coherence in terminology and transversal communication of key messages. In addition to conceptual differences among project partners, this risk might arise also due to differences in language, disciplinary perspectives, and cultural nuances.

Within Task 2.1 of the project, the project has developed a conceptual framework which can support in mitigating this risk. This framework provides a cohesive understanding of key concepts and can serve as a guide for aligning communication efforts within the project consortium and throughout the project lifecycle. It serves as a reference point for all project deliverables and ensures consistency in messaging across all project partners, both nationally and internationally. Furthermore, the conceptual framework will be actively utilised to guide discussions within the TRANS-lighthouses consortium. This collaborative approach ensures that all partners are on the same page regarding terminology and the project's key messages.

In summary, the conceptual framework plays a crucial role in mitigating the risk of coherence in terminology and communication/key messages within international and interdisciplinary projects like TRANS-Lighthouses. By providing a structured approach to conceptualising and communicating key project concepts, it fosters alignment, clarity, and consistency across all project activities and stakeholders.

5.1.2. Communications critical risks as screened for grant preparation

Communications critical risks as screened for grant preparation		
Risk #	Description / Proposed mitigation measures	WP
2	Internal communication problems (low) Review communication plan; improve the channels and focal points for communication.	WP1
8	Continuous impacts of COVID-19, restrictions for in-person meetings (medium -high) Use of digital tools, formats and meetings, work in small groups, host meetings in open-air settings in nature where safety and physical distance can be achieved easily, 1:1 formats etc.	WP3
9	Engagement of stakeholders and citizens not so familiar with digital tools (low) Toolbox with approaches to address and target these groups, work package 6 dedicated to this topic.	WP3
18	Stakeholders expectation mismatch for the project outputs (medium) Transparent and clear communication on the scientific outputs that are prioritised and expected in the research (i.e. why, how, what).	WP6
19	Digital and low tech issues: Tools appropriation, delivery delay, technical limitations Propose many options to resolve problems.	WP6

Table 37: Communications critical risks as screened for grant preparation

5.1.3. SWOT analysis - Dissemination capacity of partners (Sep. 2023)

SWOT analysis - Capacity for dissemination of partners, based on communications survey 1 (Sep. 2023)

STRENGTHS

- > AI use on Community communication and citizen science in some team
- > Many communication vectors and materials: Email, Web, Newsletter, Social networks (Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, Tik Tok, Youtube...), Street action
- > All scales in terms of population and entities
- > All teams agree with WP6 objectives
- > Objectives address EU recommendations
- > Objectives in line with project's transversal dimension
- > Objectives promote a holistic and effective approach to community-centred communication and e+ngagement.
- > Objectives involve the distinct dimensions of NBS communication
- > Digital devices or app
- > Gender equality sensibility
- > Different civil society organisations acting in the territories
- > All the teams have dissemination's capacity for the project results
- > The majority of the teams have someone responsible for communication
- > Ability for each team to call for participation when advertising an event or a call to action
- > Same monitoring indicators are needed for communication strategy assessment

WEAKNESSES

- > Youth and women are not clearly identified as target populations
- > Terminologies to precise or include: - dissemination - exploitation - "unlearning" - equitable participation - bidirectional - community empowerment and decentralisation
- > Include communication coming from the "outside" with project
- > Concrete tangible dimension of communication is missing
- > Some societies are not really "all inclusive" in terms of population origin
- > Two teams don't have someone dedicated/responsible for the communication management
- > No systematic/ professionalised dissemination of work to broader audience and civil society and lack of (human) resources to be very active "on the ground" and beyond projects (both are not rewarded by academic system)
- > Only a few numbers of teams make impact assessment after a communication campaign
- > In some teams:
 - Some communication departments are often overwhelmed.
 - Lack of internal communication department; lack of human resources with training in communication area
 - Lot to transfer to the local governments, with risk of overwhelming them with too much information and possible action items
 - Bureaucracy
 - Very small team
 - Lack of financial resources.
 - The academic calendar and the overload professors/researchers and students
 - The Location (kind of far from the City centre) reduce the possibilities of having own resources to reach the community, but will keep on working the synergies with other NGOs and entities)
 - Political adversary
 - HR need to particular project, fragmentation of network and administration
 - Impact of social communication
 - Big machine (institutional communication service)
 - Little organisation for communications support
 - Lack of training of the communications office team in specific area of project

OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Continued commitment of the EU in NBS > Possibility to create a space for the customization of a 'NBS communication' > Media Ownership and pluralism (Belgium) > Different communication styles to prepare (formal and informal) > Diversity of public > Very active organisations (NGOs) in the territory that are carrying out communication actions > Diversity of languages: English, French, Portuguese, Spanish, Swahili, German > In some teams: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publishing research results, interesting work and results to offer, knowledge also on interpretation, education (forest pedagogics!) and target groups for communication - Existing communication department - Team commitment to the proper development of the project; partner media with local newspaper (biweekly page); website to be able to function as a local link of the TRANS-lighthouses project - Close connections to municipalities in the Global South. - Researcher network specialised in various aspects of local democracy - Organisation are already well-known and prestigious - Pre-existing network with communication experience, well-structured news websites, broad reach, diversity focus, experience in environmental topics - Already active social networks / students can participate in the processes / other project where partners are involved and the direct participation of some of the members of the team in other Horizon projects - Large network, communication team and political visibility - Expertise in communicating science; good overall perspective of the target groups. > Scale of students, professors, employees. > Communication service already established for the top institutional level. Project teams already familiar with some communication tools like blogs or CMS administration. > Close collaboration with case and expertise in partitives methods > Existence of a communications office 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Flexibility/openness to adapt if new needs are identified or expressed > Adaptability > Conduct communication in the traditional or mainstream way; lack of innovation > Use the right material at the right level across institutions > Verified information > Coherence of communication strategy > Many political constraints: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct link or ongoing collaboration with political entities - Be careful about expressing opinions that are politically sensitive - Language requirements - Media regulation authorities > Tradition and religion forces > Be GDPR compliant > Various literacy rate > Citizens themselves are hard to involve > Some entities have their own communication strategies > "Bureaucratic" language (project presentation on CORDIS website) > Conventional administrative regard, some established centralised culture can be an opponent > Male-centred communities > Strong presence of industry in some territories and communities

NEEDS

- For an academic institution, more and more professionalised outreach and dissemination to broader audiences - professional social media activities, better transfer of knowledge and bringing things "to the ground"
- Difficult to realise: time and in-person exchanges with actors "on the ground", supporting them in their efforts to get solutions implemented
- A vision on community-based communication in the context of a communication department in a big university
- Training, partnership in the diversification of channels and media
- Clearly defined angles of how the results are useful for communities in the Global South, and easily adaptable formats
- Researchers' time and efforts to participate in conference or learning opportunities with other local democracy researchers
- Facilitate team building and time management
- Larger funding to expand the team
- To involve more people (administrative / colleagues/ students) in the project communication needs
- Management of different actors, knowledge of hierarchical structure and political position of hexarchy, trust from associations and citizens
- External communication services, capacitation
- Integration between mailing lists and social networks
- Need support to identify which information is relevant or not for which media
- Support decided and available in the consortia is welcomed
- Involvement and training of the communications office team

Table 38: SWOT analysis - Capacity for dissemination of partners, based on the results of communications survey 1 (Sep. 2023)

5.2. Ethics compliance

In addition to the aforementioned ethical guidelines regarding images and messages ([Dóchas Guide to Ethical Communications 2023](#)), the TRANS-lighthouses project has its ethical compliance set out in:

- *Task 2.5:*
 - establishment of the principles and procedures to resolution and mediation of any conflicts and ethics issues;
 - establishment of local mechanism/focal point to respond to the ethics, human rights and gender issues in each local context;
 - continuous monitoring of the adequacy of procedures, methods and principles application;
 - development of guidelines (deliverable D2.1) co-constructed according to the conceptual framework of work package 2, including specificities, e.g. childhood, gender, functional diversity, older adults, race and ethnicity, citizenship status (migrant/refugee/asylum seeker condition), religious diversity, and priority groups of the project;
 - provision of ethics, gender and human rights indicators to be monitored and for the assessment of the project compliance with "Do No Significant Harm" principle (article 17 EU regulation 2020/852);
 - formulation of a code of ethics and conduct, inspired by human-nature and co-production principles.
- *Work package 7:*
 - consisting of 4 deliverables that sets out the 'ethics requirements' the project must comply with for any activity raising ethical issues;
 - appointment of 1 external independent ethics commission (deliverable D7.1);
 - provision of templates necessary for compliance with ethical procedures, including informed consent, information sheet, withdrawal declaration, among others.

In the framework of the OEI - Requirement No. 1 (deliverable D7.1), an External Ethical Advisory Board (EEAB) has been established, which will be activated during the first year of the project. The EEAB will ensure adherence to the ethical guidelines that will be defined in task 2.5 (deliverable D2.1 - Guide on research ethics and inclusive participation for NBS) and according to the highest ethical standards, namely [GDPR](#), [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#), [Horizon Europe Guide on Ethics and Data Protection](#) (2021), [Horizon Europe Guide on Ethics in Social Sciences and Humanities](#) (2021). The documents produced and decisions taken by the EEAB will be carried out in line with these ethical standards. The international and national laws on ethical principles in each country are also involved, and the EEAB will guide its action and promote the commitment to respect EU-based values, such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities.

Accordingly, the project activities that include data collection will be designed to respect and maintain privacy regulations, as mandated by GDPR. All participants of such activities will be explicitly informed through written documents about the way their data will be handled, the purpose of their usage, who will have access to them, as well as their own rights in their data, while they will be requested to declare their agreement to these approaches through a consent form. No personal data will be collected unless absolutely necessary. In such cases, personal data will be stored in secure servers with access to them granted only to specific persons of the consortium.

Moreover, in relation to activities of communication, dissemination and exploitation of results, specific attention is to be paid to informed consent, as well as to disclosing information about assessment and pilot cases through the external communication channels.

5.3. Data privacy

The TRANS-lighthouses' data management plan (v1, deliverable D1.2) outlines the specifics of the data that will be collected and/or generated through the entire span of the project, i.e. all data deriving from every activity that will be performed in the context of the project.

As regard to data privacy, as established in the data management plan:

- All project data will be stored to Google Drive cloud servers using a commercial, non-public licence of Google Workspace that meets privacy and security requirements to comply with GDPR.
- The administrator of the Google Drive/Workspace account will ensure that access to the data will only be possible to project team members according to a data classification policy that will organise them into user groups determined by the steering committee.
- The identification of the team members will be ensured by using authentication processes.
- In compliance with [GDPR](#), a data region policy will be set to ensure that data are stored exclusively to servers geographically located in Europe.
- The project TRANS-lighthouses includes participants from 7 non-EU countries, in particular Argentina, Brazil, Chile, India, Kenya, Tanzania and USA. Among these, Argentina and USA (organisations participating in the EU-US Data Privacy Framework) have been recognized by the European Commission as providing adequate data protection.
- For the cases where data privacy adequacy has not been decided by the European Commission, compliance with [GDPR](#) will be ensured by contractual agreements between the project coordinator and the non-EU participant, in which the latter should confirm adherence to the requirements of [GDPR](#) (contractual agreements to be included in the second version of the data management plan (v2, deliverable D1.8)).

Moreover, as regard to TRANS-lighthouses' website (www.trans-lighthouses.eu):

- A Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificate was purchased by CES-UC for the address trans-lighthouses.eu in order to encrypt communications between the server and visitors.
- The website will also clearly communicate its privacy policy and data handling practices, quality and [GDPR](#) policy, including a cookies disclaimer.

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Annex 1. Communications survey: assessment of objectives, environment and communicative capacity of partners (Sep. 2023)

Communications survey: assessment of objectives, environment and communicative capacity of partners	
1. Contribution, doubt, or disagreement on communication goals	Overview of results
> Contribution, doubt, or disagreement on communication goals (task 1.5)	<u>Under compilation and analysis for assessment/review workshop</u>
> Contribution, doubt, or disagreement on the objectives of work package 6	
> Another relevant communication objective to consider	
2. Partners' communication environment	Overview of results
> Legal/political constraints on and limitations to the use of mass media or traditional channels	
> Existing media coverage area	
> Style and scope of the usual communication (literacy rate, interpersonal vs. media, geographic and cultural diversity)	
> Involvement culture of the private sector and civil society in development-related communication activities	
> Political dynamics: including supporters and opponents of community empowerment and decentralisation efforts, power factors	
> Cultural characteristics and diversity: language and religious diversity, traditions regarding gender roles, common symbols and customs that should be accounted	
> Role and capacity of civil society: - the extent of involvement of civil society (including community-based organisations, advocacy groups, NGOs, academics, intellectuals, journalists, and others) in public dialogue and - its capacity to facilitate community mobilisation, information campaigns, monitoring and evaluation efforts, and other activities	
> Existing related development efforts and communication campaigns: synergies, scale economies, and partnership and learning opportunities, particularly in communities empowerment projects related to NBS	
3. Communicative capacity of the partners' organisation/entity	Overview of results
> Organisation capacity (town/city/region/country) to be an active agent in disseminating the project and its results: - lots of capacity - quite - bit - no capacity (need support) - other	
> Capacity for dissemination of the project and its results, as well as the practical cases, the pilot and/or the knowledge living labs: - strengths - weaknesses - needs - other	
> If there is someone responsible for communication in the partners' organisation/entity: - a person from the entity dedicated exclusively to communication - an agency or external specialist - a person in the organisation who performs other activities - do it together the best we know how - nobody	
> Level of experience of the responsible for communication: - graduate in journalism/communication/public relations/other, with more than 10 years of experience - not licensed, but with knowledge learned in practice and good results - with some knowledge and does what can with what knows - others	

> Communication tasks carried out by communication officer:
- plan communication design and strategy - evaluation of results - implementation of communication campaigns - press office (press releases, press clippings, press conferences) - content writing (journalism or marketing) - storytelling - newsletter - mailing - community manager - graphic design - video making - organisation of congresses and events and other calls with assistance - speaker - SEO/SEM - others

> Channels used to communicate, inform, disseminate, calls:
- phone - email - web - blog - newsletter - chats (Telegram, Whatsapp, Discord,..others) - social networks (Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, Tik Tok, Youtube...) - mass media - local media - talks or lectures in public - street action - workshops - others

> Having a support network for dissemination (agenda, contact list, mailing, other):
- activist - researchers - institutions - politicians - local - regional - national - European - international - others

> Practice of impact assessment when disseminating information, convening or publishing a study

> Examples of communication/dissemination/participation actions carried out in 2023, and links to communicative actions

> Ability to call for participation when advertising an event or a call to action

> Usual evaluation of communication activities

4. Key performance indicators (KPI) for measuring and evaluate strategic performance of actions

Overview of results

> Use of visibility indicators
- social media: rate or number of impressions, number of visits, total number of subscribers or followers, number of views on a video, none, other KPIs
- website: number of unique users, rate of new visitors, none, other KPIs
- newsletter: number of subscribers, rate of deliverability, none, other KPIs

> Engagement indicators
- social media: total number of interactions (likes, shares, comments), number of subscribers gained, rate of clicks, engagement rate, other KPIs
- website: bounce rate, engagement rate, number of pages visited per session, number of visitors per channel (direct, organic, ads, social media...), none, other KPIs
- newsletters: opening rate, click-through rate, unsubscribe rate, none, other KPIs

> Conversion: number of messages received, rate of conversion of visitors into leads, number of subscribers/registers to a newsletter or webinar, none, other KPIs

> Sentiment: positive, neutral, negative, none, other KPIs

> Other relevant KPIs

5. Communication contacts and channels

Overview of results

> Contact person responsible for communication at the partners' organisation/entity
- communicational interface with the WP6 and Task 1.5
- at least 1 contact person for the communication area
>> Entity name / Name and surname of the communication or contact person / Email address of the communication or contact person / Another way to contact

Communication channels: addresses of the communication channels of the partners' organisation/entity

Table 39: Communications survey: assessment of objectives, environment and communicative capacity of partners (Sep. 2023)